

The mechanisms of potassium loss in acute myocardial ischemia: new insights from computational simulations

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Acute myocardial ischemia induces hyperkalemia (accumulation of extracellular potassium), a
4 major perpetrator of lethal reentrant ventricular arrhythmias. Despite considerable experimental
5 efforts to explain this pathology in the last decades, the intimate mechanisms behind hyperkalemia
6 remain partially unknown. In order to investigate these mechanisms, we developed a novel
7 computational model of acute myocardial ischemia which couples (a) an electrophysiologically
8 detailed human cardiomyocyte model that incorporates modifications to account for ischemia-
9 induced changes in transmembrane currents, with (b) a model of cardiac tissue and extracellular
10 K^+ transport. The resulting model is able to reproduce and explain the triphasic time course of
11 extracellular K^+ concentration within the ischemic zone, with values of $[K^+]_o$ close to 14 mmol/L
12 in the central ischemic zone after 30 minutes. In addition, the formation of a $[K^+]_o$ border zone
13 of approximately 1.2 cm 15 minutes after the onset of ischemia is predicted by the model. Our
14 results indicate that the primary rising phase of $[K^+]_o$ is mainly due to the imbalance between
15 K^+ efflux, that increases slightly, and K^+ influx, that follows a reduction of the NaK pump activity
16 by more than 50%. The onset of the plateau phase is caused by the appearance of electrical
17 alternans (a novel mechanism identified by the model), which cause an abrupt reduction in the
18 K^+ efflux. After the plateau, the secondary rising phase of $[K^+]_o$ is caused by a subsequent
19 imbalance between the K^+ influx, which continues to decrease slowly, and the K^+ efflux, which
20 remains almost constant. Further, the study shows that the modulation of these mechanisms by
21 the electrotonic coupling is the main responsible for the formation of the ischemic border zone
22 in tissue, with K^+ transport playing only a minor role. Finally, the results of the model indicate
23 that the injury current established between the healthy and the altered tissue is not sufficient to
24 depolarize non-ischemic cells within the healthy tissue.

25 **Keywords:** hyperkalemia, myocardial ischemia, injury current, computational model, alternans, potassium loss

1 INTRODUCTION

26 Globally, cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains the leading cause of death and disability, accounting for
27 around 18.5 million deaths every year, approximately one third of all deaths globally (Roth et al., 2020).
28 Among CVD, atherosclerotic coronary artery disease is the most common pathology. This disease may
29 cause a partial or complete occlusion of a coronary artery which, in turn, causes myocardial ischemia and
30 infarction. If ischemia is regional (the most common case) and affects only a part of the myocardium,
31 it introduces abnormal heterogeneity in the tissue. Indeed, resting membrane potential, action potential
32 (AP) duration and effective refractory period, among others, may differ from one site to another. This
33 ischemia-induced heterogeneity provides an important pro-arrhythmic substrate (Kléber, 1984; Janse and
34 Wit, 1989; Coronel, 1994).

35 The acute phase of myocardial ischemia corresponds to the first 30-60 minutes after coronary artery
36 occlusion and is associated with a high incidence of arrhythmic events (Smith et al., 1995; Yan et al., 2004;
37 Cascio et al., 2005). During the first 30 minutes, the period in which this study will focus, ischemia is
38 characterized by important metabolic changes inducing profound electrophysiological alterations in the
39 behavior of affected cardiomyocytes. The main metabolic changes include a reduction in intracellular
40 adenosine triphosphate (ATP), changes in intracellular adenosine diphosphate (ADP), a reduction of tissue
41 pH, and an increase in lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) (Daleau, 1999; Sakamoto et al., 2000; Terkildsen
42 et al., 2007). These changes cause alterations in the cell resting membrane potential, which becomes
43 less negative, and modulate the inward and outward transmembrane currents, leading to hyperkalemia
44 (an increase in extracellular potassium concentration, $[K^+]_o$). In the time domain, direct assessment of
45 potassium loss during acute ischemia in different animal models has identified a time course of $[K^+]_o$
46 characterized by three distinctive phases (Hill and Gettes, 1980; Wilde and Aksnes, 1995; Coronel et al.,
47 1991). A few seconds after the occlusion, $[K^+]_o$ begins to rise, reaching a plateau or experiencing a minor
48 decline after approximately 5 to 10 minutes after the onset of ischemia. After the plateau phase, a secondary
49 rise in $[K^+]_o$ occurs. Interestingly, this triphasic pattern has been observed in different animal models (Hill
50 and Gettes, 1980; Weiss and Shine, 1982a; Coronel et al., 1988; Wilde and Aksnes, 1995) under different
51 stimulation frequencies (Harper et al., 1993; Wilde and Aksnes, 1995). In the spatial domain, a central
52 ischemic zone (CIZ), within which cells exhibit the highest degree of hyperkalemia, dynamically develops.
53 The CIZ is surrounded by an ischemic border zone (BZ) of around 1 cm, within which cells are partially
54 affected by hyperkalemia, which declines towards the myocardial normal zone (Hill and Gettes, 1980;
55 Coronel et al., 1988, 1991).

56 The increase in extracellular potassium is related to alterations of the electrical behavior of ischemic
57 cardiomyocytes (Janse and Wit, 1989). Specifically, resting membrane potential increases (which reduces
58 cell excitability), action potential duration shortens and conduction velocity diminishes, among other
59 alterations. These electrophysiological changes provide a potential substrate for the generation of arrhythmic
60 events leading to ventricular fibrillation and sudden cardiac death (Harris et al., 1954; Smith et al., 1995).
61 The evidence comes from experiments involving isolated whole hearts subject to regional acute myocardial
62 ischemia (Harris et al., 1954; Janse et al., 1980; Janse and Kléber, 1981; Weiss and Shine, 1981, 1982b;
63 Coronel et al., 1989; Janse and Wit, 1989; Coronel, 1994; Weiss et al., 2017). In these experiments,
64 ischemia (and hyperkalemia in particular) was found to promote unidirectional block and reentry due to
65 the partial or complete loss of cell excitability provoked by extracellular potassium accumulation. Also, the
66 appearance of an “injury current” flowing from the ischemic zone to the normal zone has been hypothesized
67 to induce a source-sink imbalance which could induce ectopic activity that would act as a trigger for
68 reentry (Janse et al., 1980; Janse and van Capelle, 1982; Coronel et al., 1991; Coronel, 1994). Computer

69 simulations have also highlighted the arrhythmogenic effects of ischemia-induced hyperkalemia in virtual
70 2D tissues (Ferrero et al., 2003; Trénor et al., 2007; Tice et al., 2007; Romero et al., 2009) and 3D virtual
71 bi-ventricular heart models (Mena Tobar et al., 2018; Carpio et al., 2022).

72 Despite the importance of this phenomenon, and the number of experimental studies trying to elucidate
73 the ionic and tissue related mechanisms behind the increase in $[K^+]_o$ (Kléber, 1984; Wilde and Aksnes,
74 1995; Weiss and Shine, 1982a; Hill and Gettes, 1980; Coronel et al., 1988, 1991), the intimate mechanisms
75 responsible for extracellular potassium accumulation are still uncertain (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995;
76 Shivkumar et al., 1997; Weiss et al., 2017). In particular, the relative individual contributions of the
77 different ionic currents to extracellular potassium accumulation has yet to be established. Also, the triphasic
78 nature of the $[K^+]_o$ time course (Kléber, 1984) remains to be fully explained. Most of the experimental
79 work was conducted from the late 1970s to the early 1990s, and the fact that few new experimental reports
80 have been published since then may be due to the difficulty in designing new experiments to obtain further
81 evidence of the hyperkalemia mechanisms.

82 Indeed, using solely experimental means to elucidate the intimate mechanisms responsible for $[K^+]_o$
83 accumulation has severe limitations, as it is not currently possible to record individual transmembrane
84 ionic currents simultaneously with the APs and $[K^+]_o$ in cardiac tissue during acute ischemia. For this
85 reason, efforts have been made to use computational simulations using electrophysiologically detailed
86 models of the AP and its underlying transmembrane ionic currents to explore the mechanisms behind
87 this phenomenon (Rodríguez et al., 2002; Terkildsen et al., 2007; Potse et al., 2007a,b; Niederer, 2013).
88 Although these models were able to partially explain ischemia-induced hyperkalemia, they suffered from
89 important limitations that hindered the soundness of the results. In the pioneering work by Rodríguez
90 et al. (2002), the study was only carried out in a single isolated virtual guinea pig cardiomyocyte and was
91 limited to the initial potassium rise and the plateau. In a subsequent study, Terkildsen et al. (2007) also
92 addressed the mechanisms of the secondary potassium rise but, similarly to the former study, it was limited
93 to an isolated cardiomyocyte and did not account for tissue effects. Later, the role of potassium transport
94 in the development of the potassium BZ was studied in a biventricular human heart model (Potse et al.,
95 2007a,b). However, the model assumed a constant net potassium efflux from the cells, thus uncoupling
96 the electrophysiological behavior of the cell from the extracellular potassium accumulation. Finally, the
97 spatio-temporal evolution of ionic concentrations across the ischemic BZ was then studied in Niederer
98 (2013) by means of a model of cardiac tissue accounting for the diffusion of different metabolites coupled
99 with an electrophysiologically detailed model of the AP. However, the model only considers the diastolic
100 currents, neglecting the electrical excitation and propagation within the tissue. Even though the model
101 predicts the potassium efflux and the diffusion of extracellular potassium, the size of the BZ and the
102 maximum $[K^+]_o$ are much smaller than those reported experimentally (Coronel, 1994).

103 Understanding the mechanisms that lead to hyperkalemia would enable a better understanding of its
104 arrhythmogenic effects and the development of more solid approaches to its treatment. With this in mind,
105 this work attempts to study, with the aid of computer simulations, the intimate mechanisms underlying
106 the increase in $[K^+]_o$ during the first 30 minutes after the onset of ischemia. For this purpose, a novel
107 electrophysiologically detailed model of the ischemic cell and tissue was developed. The cellular model is
108 based on the O'Hara model of the human ventricular cardiac AP (O'Hara et al., 2011), modified to simulate
109 ischemia by incorporating the effects of ischemia-related metabolites on ionic transmembrane currents.
110 The model also includes an extra equation to account for the dynamic changes in extracellular potassium.
111 The model was then coupled to a tissue model which includes electrophysiology-transport equations to
112 investigate the spatial and temporal dispersion of $[K^+]_o$ across the ischemic BZ. Ionic concentrations,

113 potassium fluxes across the cell membrane, the transmembrane potential and the extracellular potential
114 were monitored to elucidate the basis of cellular potassium loss during acute myocardial ischemia.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

115 2.1 Virtual tissue description

116 In this work, “0D simulations” corresponds to a virtual single isolated ventricular cardiomyocyte, and
117 “1D simulations” to a virtual myocardial one-dimensional strand 4 cm in length. In the latter case, in order
118 to simulate regional ischemia, the first 2 cm correspond to normal cells (“normoxic tissue”), whereas the
119 rest of the fiber was subject to ischemic conditions (“altered tissue”), as described below.

120 2.2 Action potential model

121 Unless otherwise stated, the simulations were carried out using a modified version of the O’Hara
122 model (O’Hara et al., 2011). This model is widely accepted to simulate APs and the underlying ionic
123 currents in human ventricular cardiomyocytes, and was adopted by an expert group of the FDA as the
124 starting point for developing an *in-silico* model suitable for regulatory decision making (Colatsky et al.,
125 2016). The model includes mathematical descriptions of fifteen transmembrane currents flowing through
126 ion channels, pumps and exchangers, as well as the calcium transients involved in the calcium-induced
127 calcium release process, and calcium buffering in the intracellular medium. In particular, the model includes
128 seven different ionic currents that carry potassium ions, namely the rapid delayed rectifier potassium current
129 (I_{Kr}), the slow delayed rectifier potassium current (I_{Ks}), the transient outward potassium current (I_{to}),
130 the inward rectifier potassium current (I_{K1}), the background potassium current (I_{Kb}), the potassium
131 component of the L-type calcium current (I_{CaL}) and the sodium/potassium (NaK) pump (I_{NaK}).

132 To obtain realistic values of AP upstroke velocity and propagation velocity, the formulation of I_{Na} and
133 I_{NaL} were modified as in Carpio et al. (2019) (which, in turn, includes the modifications by Dutta et al.
134 (2017)).

135 2.3 Cellular model of acute ischemia

136 To simulate the effects of acute myocardial ischemia at the cell membrane level, more profound changes
137 were made to the O’Hara model (as in Carpio et al. (2022)). First, a model of the ATP-sensitive potassium
138 current ($I_{K(ATP)}$), which is absent in the O’Hara model, was formulated using the model by Ferrero
139 et al. (1996) adapted to human cardiomyocytes using data from Babenko et al. (1998) by changing the
140 maximum conductance and the sensitivity to intracellular ATP and ADP concentrations ($[ATP]_i$ and
141 $[ADP]_i$, respectively). Secondly, the effects of $[ATP]_i$ and $[ADP]_i$ on ionic pumps were modeled using
142 data from Cortassa et al. (2006) and Terkildsen et al. (2007) by introducing different $[ATP]_i$ and $[ADP]_i$
143 dependent scaling factors affecting the NaK pump (I_{NaK}), the sarcolemmal calcium pump (I_{pCa}) and the
144 SERCA pump (I_{up}). Thirdly, we introduced the effects of extracellular and intracellular acidosis in the
145 model by applying different multiplicative factors that depend on pH_o and/or pH_i to several pH-dependent
146 currents. Specifically, we used data from Saegusa et al. (2011) to model the effects of acidosis in I_{CaL} ; data
147 from Murphy et al. (2011) and Watson and Gold (1995) for both I_{Na} and I_{NaL} ; data from Doering et al.
148 (1996) and Egger and Niggli (2000) for the sodium/calcium exchanger (I_{CaNa}); and data from Friedrich
149 et al. (1996) to model the effects of acidosis on I_{NaK} . Finally, the effects of lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC)
150 on I_{Na} and I_{NaL} were modeled following Gautier et al. (2008).

151 2.4 Simulation of progressive acute ischemia

152 Each simulation corresponds to 5 minutes of normoxia followed by 30 minutes of acute ischemia. During
153 this 30 minute period, hypoxia and acidosis are progressive, and the time evolution of the ischemic
154 parameters is shown in Fig 1A through D. For the $[ATP]_i$ (Fig 1A), the time course reported by Sakamoto
155 et al. (2000) for guinea pig was adopted with a normoxic value of $[ATP]_i=10$ mmol/L as in O'Hara
156 et al. (2011) and Cao et al. (2018). Regarding pH (Fig 1C), the time course of pH_i reported by Sakamoto
157 et al. (2000) for guinea pig was assumed. The same time course was adopted for pH_o , with a normoxic
158 value of $pH_o=7.4$ measured in guinea pig (Vaughan-Jones et al., 2009). For $[LPC]_i$, a linear time course
159 was assumed with a normoxic value of $[LPC]_i=2\mu\text{mol/L}$ and a concentration of $[LPC]_i=20\mu\text{mol/L}$ at 30
160 minutes from the onset of ischemia, estimated from the works by Sobel et al. (1978) and Daleau (1999).
161 As for free intracellular ADP, due to its low basal concentrations, direct measurements of $[ADP]_i$ are not
162 possible and must be estimated using mass-action kinetics principles. In this regard, different profiles of
163 ADP have been derived (Allen and Orchard, 1987; Weiss et al., 1992; Terkildsen et al., 2007). In this work,
164 the ADP profile derived by Terkildsen et al. (2007) has been adopted.

165 In the 1D simulations, these dynamic changes affected only the “altered tissue”, while in the “normoxic
166 tissue” the values of the parameters remained normal ($[ATP]_i=10$ mmol/L, $[ADP]_i=15\mu\text{mol/L}$, $pH_i=7.2$,
167 $pH_o=7.4$, and $[LPC]_i=2\mu\text{mol/L}$). In the case of $[ATP]_i$, $[ADP]_i$ and $[LPC]_i$, these dynamic changes
168 have been imposed in a stepwise manner at the transition between the normal and ischemic tissue, as
169 indicated in the study from Walfridsson et al. (1985) that reports the anoxic border to develop in less than
170 1 mm. On the contrary, a transition zone of 0.5 cm has been considered for pH_i and pH_o following the
171 model by Ferrero et al. (2003) which was inspired in the studies from Coronel et al. (1988). Figure 1E
172 shows the spatial transition for the cyanotic and the acidosis border used in the simulations.

173 Due to the large variability of the data present in the literature, additional simulations considering different
174 time-courses and baseline values for the different metabolites were performed for completeness. Results
175 from these simulations are available as part of the Supplementary Material (Figs S1 and S3) and will be
176 discussed later.

177 2.5 Stimulation protocol

178 The cell (in the “0D simulations”) and the first (leftmost) cell of the “normoxic tissue” (in the “1D
179 simulations”) were stimulated during 35 minutes with a train of pulses 0.5 milliseconds in width and
180 twice normoxic diastolic threshold in amplitude, with a frequency of 1 Hz (unless otherwise stated). The
181 frequency of 1Hz was chosen since most of the experimental studies found in the literature were conducted
182 at this frequency. However, to test the sensitivity of the model to heart rate, additional simulations were
183 carried out in which the cell was paced at different frequencies: i) a quiescent cell (0 beats per minute,
184 bpm), ii) a bradycardic situation (30 bpm), iii) our control heart rate (60 bpm), iv) a mild tachycardia (120
185 bpm), and v) a severe tachycardia (180 bpm).

186 2.6 Tissue electrophysiology equations

187 In the 1D simulations, cardiac tissue was modeled as a continuous fiber with a length L of 4 cm. The
188 transmembrane potential (V_m), and the extracellular potential (V_o), were computed using the bidomain
189 model in two steps (Keller et al., 2010). First, V_m was obtained as the solution of the 1D reaction-diffusion

190 equation:

$$C_m \frac{\partial V_m}{\partial t} = D_V \frac{\partial^2 V_m}{\partial x^2} - I_{ion} + I_{stm} \quad (1)$$

191 where D_V is the effective tissue conductivity, C_m is the specific membrane capacitance, I_{ion} is the
 192 transmembrane ionic current density (sum of the transmembrane currents included in the O'Hara model),
 193 and I_{stm} is the stimulation current density. The extracellular potential is governed by the following partial
 194 differential equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 V_o}{\partial x^2} = -\frac{1}{1 + \lambda} \frac{\partial^2 V_m}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

195 where λ is the extracellular to intracellular conductivity ratio. Eq 1 and Eq 2 are subject to non conduction
 196 boundary conditions at both cable ends

$$\frac{\partial V_m}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \text{at } x = 0 \text{ and } x = L \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial V_o}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \text{at } x = 0 \text{ and } x = L \quad (4)$$

197 In the “0D simulations”, Eq 1 without the diffusion term was used:

$$C_m \frac{dV_m}{dt} = -I_{ion} + I_{stm} \quad (5)$$

198 2.7 Computation of the injury current

199 One of the interests of this study was to investigate on the characteristics of the “injury current” which
 200 flows between the altered and normal tissue during acute ischemia, and to evaluate its potential role in
 201 arrhythmogenesis during acute myocardial ischemia (Janse and Kléber, 1981; Coronel et al., 1991). For
 202 this purpose the intracellular injury current, I_i^{inj} , was computed through the following differential equation

$$I_i^{inj} = D_V \frac{\partial^2 V_m}{\partial x^2}. \quad (6)$$

203 This equation is computed as a postprocessing step in the simulations.

204 2.8 Potassium transport equations

205 To model the dynamic changes in extracellular potassium concentration ($[K^+]_o$), in the “1D simulations”
 206 we used a modified version of the Nernst-Planck equation (Niederer, 2013) to formulate a transport
 207 equation for K^+ . The equation accounts for diffusion, electromigration, and also for the local contribution
 208 of transmembrane ionic currents and wash-out:

$$\frac{\partial [K^+]_o}{\partial t} = D_K \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial [K^+]_o}{\partial x} + \frac{F}{RT} [K^+]_o \frac{\partial V_o}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{A_c}{F v_o} \sum_x I_{Kx} + \frac{[K^+]_b - [K^+]_o}{\tau_{wo}}, \quad (7)$$

209 where D_K is the extracellular potassium diffusion coefficient, F is the Faraday's constant, R is the gas
 210 constant, T is the absolute temperature, V_o is the extracellular potential, A_c is the cell surface, v_o is the
 211 volume of the extracellular compartment, $\sum I_{Kx}$ the total transmembrane potassium current ($I_{Kr} + I_{Ks}$
 212 $+ I_{to} + I_{K1} + I_{K(ATP)} + I_{Kb} + I_{CaK} - 2I_{NaK}$), $[K^+]_b$ the bulk extracellular potassium concentration

213 present in the blood stream, and τ_{wo} is the time constant associated with potassium wash-out (from the
 214 extracellular clefts to the blood flow). Eq 7 is subject to no-diffusion boundary conditions at the cable ends

$$\frac{\partial [K^+]_o}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \text{at } x = 0 \text{ and } x = L. \quad (8)$$

215 In the “0D simulations”, Eq 7 without the diffusion term was used:

$$\frac{d[K^+]_o}{dt} = \frac{A_c}{Fv_o} \sum_x I_{Kx} + \frac{[K^+]_b - [K^+]_o}{\tau_{wo}}, \quad (9)$$

216 2.9 Computation of potassium flux rates

217 One of the objectives of this study was to compute the contribution of each individual sarcolemmal
 218 current to extracellular potassium accumulation. For this purpose, we define the potassium flux rate (K_{FRx})
 219 generated by a particular potassium current I_{Kx} as the rate of increase of $[K^+]_o$ directly provoked by that
 220 current (averaged in a certain time interval, corresponding to 4 beats unless otherwise stated). A positive
 221 value of K_{FRx} corresponds to an efflux, and a negative value to an influx.

222 From Eq 9 (particularized for a specific potassium current I_{Kx}), the value of K_{FRx} may be computed as
 223 follows:

$$K_{FRx}(t) = \frac{[K^+]_{o,(t+4 \cdot BCL)} - [K^+]_{o,(t)}}{4 \cdot BCL} = \frac{1}{4 \cdot BCL} \frac{A_c}{Fv_o} \int_t^{t+4 \cdot BCL} I_{Kx} dt \quad (10)$$

224 where BCL (Basic Cycle Length) is the stimulation period (1000 milliseconds, unless otherwise stated).

225 The total potassium flux rate (K_{FRT}) is given by:

$$K_{FRT} = \sum_x K_{FRx} \quad (11)$$

226 2.10 Numerical and computational methods

227 The “0D simulations” were performed with a custom-made script in MATLAB (MathWorks, Natick,
 228 MA) using an adaptive time step method. On the contrary, for the “1D simulations”, Eq 1 and Eq 7 were
 229 solved with an in-house C code using the operator splitting numerical scheme together with the explicit
 230 Euler method. Eq 2 was integrated with custom-made software routines in MATLAB as a postprocessing
 231 step assuming a value of $\lambda = 3.647$ from Niederer et al. (2011).

232 For the “1D simulations”, a constant time step of $\Delta t = 0.02$ ms and a space discretization of $\Delta x =$
 233 0.25 mm were used. The parameters used in the simulations are shown in Table 1. The effective tissue
 234 conductivity was assumed to be $D_V = 0.0026$ mS that gives a conduction velocity of 70 cm/s in normoxic
 235 tissue (Taggart et al., 2000). The extracellular potassium diffusion coefficient $D_K = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$ cm²/s was
 236 taken from Niederer (2013). However, additional simulations were conducted at different values of D_V and
 237 D_K to test the influence that electrotonic coupling and $[K^+]_o$ diffusion have on the formation of the $[K^+]_o$
 238 border zone. To estimate the value of the wash-out time constant in normoxia, we conducted simulations
 239 and chose a value for τ_{wo} that replicated the extracellular potassium transients observed experimentally in
 240 normoxia (Kunze, 1977; Hotokebuchi et al., 1987). An infinite value was assigned to τ_{wo} in the “altered

241 tissue” (in “1D simulations”) and in the ischemic cell (in the “0D simulations”) to mimic the lack of
242 wash-out in ischemia.

243 The accuracy of the 1D numerical simulations was verified against simulations that employed smaller
244 space and time discretizations of $\Delta x = 0.125$ mm and $\Delta t = 0.01$ ms respectively. Results indicate that
245 reducing the space discretization and time step to these values lead to an increase in the conduction velocity
246 of about 2.0%. However, major results, and main conclusions, of this study obtained with these smaller
247 time and space discretizations are still valid as discussed in the following section and reported in the
248 Supplementary Material (Fig S5).

3 RESULTS

249 3.1 Single cell simulations

250 This section describes the main results related to the “0D simulations”, corresponding to an isolated
251 ventricular cardiac myocyte.

252 3.1.1 Extracellular potassium accumulation

253 Fig 2 summarizes some of the main findings corresponding to the “0D simulations”. The solid line in
254 Fig 2A shows the time course of $[K^+]_o$ during 30 minutes of simulated progressive ischemia in the virtual
255 cardiomyocyte stimulated at 1 Hz. Data were sampled at 1 second intervals to eliminate the small “micro”
256 fluctuations (in the $\mu\text{mol}/L$ range) in $[K^+]_o$ during the systole-diastole cycle, and highlight the “macro”
257 behaviour of $[K^+]_o$. It can be seen that $[K^+]_o$ is stable before the onset of ischemia (with a value of 5.4
258 mmol/L), rises during the first ≈ 5 minutes, smoothly reaches a plateau (≈ 12 mmol/L) that lasts until the
259 fifteenth minute approximately, and then slowly increases again.

260 To test the validity of the simulation, results were compared to experimental data published
261 elsewhere (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995). The dots in Fig 2A correspond to adapted experimental data
262 of extracellular potassium accumulation obtained in rabbit hearts subject to acute global ischemia. The data
263 shown in the figure have been shifted +0.9 mmol/L to account for the difference between the normoxic
264 value of $[K^+]_o$ in Wilde and Aksnes (1995) (4.5 mmol/L) and in our simulations (5.4 mmol/L). After the
265 sixteenth minute post-occlusion, the experimentally measured $[K^+]_o$ increased faster than in our simulation
266 (not shown). In Fig S1 of the Supplementary Material, a direct comparison of our simulation with multiple
267 experimental recordings reported in different works, corresponding to a variety of animal species and/or
268 heart rates, is shown without any shift in the $[K^+]_o$ values.

269 In order to test the soundness and sensitivity of the results to the specific time courses of intracellular
270 ATP and intra/extra-cellular pH, we carried out alternative simulations using different time courses and/or
271 initial normoxic values and/or final ischemic values for said ischemic parameters. The results, which can
272 be found in Fig S2 in the Supplementary Material, show that, despite of small quantitative differences,
273 the qualitative features of the extracellular K^+ behavior remain unaltered. As for the effects of different
274 possible time courses of intracellular ADP, its effects are presented and discussed below.

275 Finally, the effect of heart rate is shown in Fig 2B. The results show that the rate of rise of extracellular
276 potassium increases with heart rate. In the particular case of a quiescent cell, the rise in $[K^+]_o$ is slow and
277 delayed, following an initial period in which a slight decrease is found.

278 3.1.2 Potassium flux rates

279 The increase in $[K^+]_o$ observed in the simulation and the experiments must be due to an imbalance
280 between potassium efflux and influx that causes a net efflux during the $[K^+]_o$ rising phase. To further
281 analyze the behaviour of potassium fluxes, we computed the potassium flux rates using Eq 10 and Eq 11
282 (see "Materials and Methods"). Fig 2C shows the time course of the different total potassium flux rates
283 (separated into "Efflux" for the unidirectional positive fluxes through potassium channels, "Influx" for the
284 unidirectional negative flux through the NaK pump, and "Net Efflux" for the difference).

285 During the normoxic period, efflux and influx are equal in magnitude ($34.5 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$), so there is no
286 net potassium efflux. As soon as ischemia begins, an imbalance between the potassium efflux and influx
287 quickly arises, with a rapid decrease in the magnitude of the influx rate being coupled to a lesser increase
288 in the efflux rate. The resulting net efflux rise (Fig 2C) during the first ≈ 4 minutes post-occlusion provokes
289 the first rising phase in $[K^+]_o$ Fig 2A.

290 Just before the fifth minute of ischemia, potassium influx has almost stabilized (at $\approx 13 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$).
291 However, the efflux rate suffers an abrupt drop, just prior to showing notorious oscillations (which are due
292 to alternans in the action potential duration (APD), as explained below). In the following two minutes, the
293 efflux keeps decreasing until it almost equals the magnitude of the influx. As a result, the net potassium
294 efflux falls to near zero values, which in turn gives rise to the plateau in $[K^+]_o$ observed in Fig 2A. After
295 several minutes, the efflux rate stabilizes in a lower value (at $\approx 10.5 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$), while the magnitude of
296 the influx suffers a slow but sustained decrease, provoking a continuous slow increase in the net potassium
297 efflux (Fig 2C). This gives rise to the secondary increase in $[K^+]_o$ observed from roughly the tenth minute
298 onwards in Fig 2A.

299 To better understand the causes of the dynamic changes in potassium efflux and influx, the individual
300 contributions of the different potassium transmembrane currents were computed using Eq 10 at selected
301 time instants depicted by the short vertical lines in Fig 3A. The results are depicted in panels B to F in Fig 3.
302 The coloured bars represent efflux rates (when positive) or influx rates (when negative). The continuous
303 data of the time course of the flux rates corresponding to the individual contributions of all the potassium
304 currents is shown in Fig S3 of the Supplementary Material.

305 As shown in Fig 3B, which corresponds to the normoxic situation just before the onset of ischemia, the
306 current carrying the highest potassium efflux is I_{Kr} , with other currents playing a minor role. Unsurprisingly,
307 the NaK pump is the only current that generates a noticeable potassium influx. At this time point, influx
308 and efflux are balanced.

309 Two and a half minutes later (Fig 3C), the most notorious change is the decrease in the magnitude of
310 the influx rate (from 34.5 to $15.0 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$) caused by the reduction in the current transported by the
311 NaK pump. Concomitantly, the efflux rates through I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$ increase considerably, counteracting
312 the decrease in the I_{Kr} efflux rate, with changes in other potassium currents being negligible. Thus, the
313 unidirectional potassium efflux increases (from 34.5 to $37.2 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$). The overall result is an increase
314 in the net efflux (from 0 to $22.2 \text{ } (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$), which provokes the primary rise in $[K^+]_o$ shown in Fig 3A.

315 Five minutes post-occlusion (Fig 3D), the efflux rates through various ion channels have considerably
316 changed. Most noticeably, the efflux generated by I_{Kr} has strongly diminished and the only currents
317 generating an appreciable potassium efflux are now I_{Kr} , I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$. Even if the influx through the
318 NaK pump has very slightly decreased, this important reduction in the efflux provokes a strong decrease in

319 the net efflux rate (now 11.2 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s). This is responsible for the decrease in the rate of rise in $[K^+]_o$
320 observed at that time in Fig 3A, which in turn begins to generate the plateau in potassium accumulation.

321 Ten minutes post-occlusion (Fig 3E), when $[K^+]_o$ has already reached the plateau, only I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$
322 generate potassium efflux, with the efflux of other potassium currents having dropped to zero. This causes
323 a strong decrease in the total efflux compared to Panel D. Meanwhile, the NaK pump has continued
324 decreasing slowly. At this time point, efflux and influx are almost equal (yielding a net efflux rate of 0.9
325 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s), which is consistent with the plateau phase in extracellular potassium seen in Fig 3A.

326 This situation is similar after 20 minutes of ischemia (Fig 3F), except that the NaK pump influx is further
327 reduced, again generating an imbalance between influx and efflux that gives rise to a net efflux of 4.5
328 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s and a secondary slow rise in $[K^+]_o$ shown in Fig 3A.

329 3.1.3 Ionic currents

330 To further investigate the causes of these changes in efflux and influx as ischemia develops, we plotted
331 the time course of APs and selected potassium currents at the time instants discussed above. The top row in
332 Fig 4 shows how APs change as ischemia progresses. Resting membrane potential becomes increasingly
333 less negative (a direct consequence of the increase in $[K^+]_o$), APD decreases (due to hyperkalemia and
334 also to the partial activation of the ATP-sensitive potassium channels), and the cell has become almost
335 non-excitable by the tenth minute. Moreover, AP alternans exist in the fifth minute post-occlusion.

336 The second row shows the progressive evolution of I_{K1} . Basically, its diastolic value keeps increasing
337 as ischemia develops due to the hump in its current-voltage relationship that implies a higher current at
338 membrane potentials moderately higher than the potassium Nernst potential (E_K). This causes the increase
339 in its associated efflux seen in Fig 3D-F.

340 The third row represents the evolution of $I_{K(ATP)}$. While it is almost nonexistent in normoxia, its
341 amplitude keeps increasing in ischemia (due to the decrease in the intracellular ATP/ADP ratio). Although
342 its duration decreases with time (due to the reduction in APD), the area below the curve (proportional to
343 the efflux generated by the current) is almost constant.

344 The fourth row shows the progression of I_{Kr} (which generates the highest potassium efflux in normoxia)
345 with ischemia. Its duration has decreased after 2.5 minutes of ischemia, thus reducing the efflux, and it has
346 almost vanished 10 minutes after the onset of ischemia (due to the cell being almost non-excitable at this
347 point). Five minutes post-occlusion, AP alternans cause an alternation in the amplitude and duration of
348 I_{Kr} , which is very low in the short AP compared to the long one. Further effects of AP alternans in the
349 time course of $[K^+]_o$ will be discussed below.

350 Finally, the lower row corresponds to the NaK pump current. The decrease in intracellular ATP levels
351 continuously reduces the magnitude of the current, thus reducing the influx of potassium as was apparent
352 in Fig 3B-F.

353 3.1.4 Action potential alternans and their effect in potassium accumulation

354 Once we identified the causes of the triphasic nature of extracellular potassium accumulation in regards
355 to potassium fluxes, we further analyzed the influence of the dynamically changing AP morphology during
356 ischemia on the time course of $[K^+]_o$.

357 The data depicted in red in the lower graph in Fig 5A represents the time course of the APD at 90%
358 repolarization (APD_{90}) during the 30 minute period of simulated ischemia at the same time scale as $[K^+]_o$
359 (upper blue graph). Immediately after the onset of ischemia, APD_{90} begins to decline, as expected. To

360 test the validity of these results, the simulated values were compared to experimental results published
361 elsewhere. The four green dots in the lower graph of Fig 5A show Monophasic Action Potential (MAP)
362 duration values (adapted by adding 32 ms to account for the basal difference with our APD_{90} values)
363 measured in acutely ischemic human hearts *in-vivo* (Sutton et al., 2000).

364 As shown in the lower graph of Panel A, between the fourth and the sixth minute of ischemia
365 (approximately), APD_{90} values begin to oscillate, indicating that the cell is developing electrical alternans.
366 This alternans phase is delimited by the dashed vertical lines. Fig 5B shows the detail of the waveform of
367 two consecutive alternating APs obtained in our simulations (at the 4.6 minute mark). At the beginning
368 of this phase, alternans with a 2:2 pattern (i.e. long - short - long - short) are predominant, but shortly
369 afterwards more complex patterns arise (e.g. long - short - short - long - long - short - long).

370 As the dashed vertical lines indicate, the period of occurrence of alternans matches the smooth transition
371 from the primary rising phase of $[K^+]_o$ to the plateau, suggesting that the alternans themselves may be
372 responsible for the gradual deceleration of the extracellular potassium rise and the genesis of the plateau.
373 To confirm this hypothesis, APs at selected time intervals spanning four consecutive APs were plotted
374 together with $[K^+]_o$. At these short time scales, $[K^+]_o$ clearly shows the “micro” fluctuations caused by
375 the systole-diastole cycles (inset in Panel A top graph), as clearly seen in the lower (blue) plots of Panels C
376 through F.

377 During normoxia (Fig 5C), APs do not alternate at all, and potassium currents are balanced in a way that
378 the diastolic minimum potassium levels (DmKL, indicated by the * signs) reach the same value at the end
379 of each diastolic period. This is consistent with the normoxic stable behaviour of the “macro” $[K^+]_o$ with
380 zero net efflux shown in Fig 2C and Fig 3B.

381 On the contrary, at the 2.5 minute mark in the ischemic cell (Fig 5D), the positive net potassium efflux
382 seen in Fig 2C and Fig 3C is related to a continuous increase in the DmKL from one AP to the following
383 one. Consequently, the “macro” $[K^+]_o$ rapidly increases. However, this trend is attenuated when alternans
384 begin to appear. Five minutes post-occlusion (Fig 5E), when the “macro” $[K^+]_o$ is decelerating (Fig 5A),
385 the difference between consecutive DmKL values diminishes in relation to Panel D. The reason is that the
386 “short” APs originate lower positive shifts in the “micro” $[K^+]_o$ fluctuations due to the fact that I_{Kr} , the
387 strongest efflux generator at the 2.5 minute mark, almost vanishes in the “short” APs (see Fig 4). This is
388 because (a) it is a systolic current that is only active during the AP, which is now short, and (b) because the
389 driving force for potassium ions is smaller due to the lesser peak of the short AP. Therefore, the average
390 potassium net efflux rate diminishes (Fig 2C and Fig 3D), causing a reduction in the slope of the “macro”
391 $[K^+]_o$ that eventually causes the plateau to appear (upper Panel A).

392 Finally, 10 minutes after the onset of ischemia (Fig 5F), only short APs are present in the cell due to
393 its partial loss of excitability provoked by an already elevated value of $[K^+]_o$ (see Panel A). In these
394 circumstances, the low positive shifts in the “micro” $[K^+]_o$ fluctuations are almost equal for consecutive
395 beats, thus the “macro” $[K^+]_o$ remains almost constant (as seen in the upper graph of Panel A).

396 3.2 Tissue simulations

397 This section describes the main results related to the “1D simulations”, corresponding to a virtual 4 cm
398 strand subject to normal conditions in its first 2 cm (the “normoxic tissue”) and to progressive acutely
399 ischemic conditions in the last 2 cm (the “altered tissue”).

400 3.2.1 Extracellular potassium accumulation

401 Fig 6A shows the spatial profiles of $[K^+]_o$ in the tissue preparation from just before and up to 30 minutes
402 after the onset of ischemia. This profile increases monotonically in the altered tissue for the first two
403 minutes post-occlusion, to then adopt a non-monotonic profile with the spatial peak increasing with time
404 and moving toward the center of the altered tissue. These changes in $[K^+]_o$ also affect a small region in the
405 distal part of the “normoxic” tissue. The position of the peak value of $[K^+]_o$ stabilizes after 15 minutes of
406 the onset of ischemia, defining an ischemic BZ of approximately 1.2 cm, in agreement with experimental
407 results (Hill and Gettes, 1980; Coronel et al., 1991). The slope of the rising phase of the $[K^+]_o$ keeps
408 increasing until minute five post-occlusion before starting to decrease, while the spatial peak of the $[K^+]_o$
409 profile moves toward the center of the ischemic zone. Around minute 15, the rising phase of the $[K^+]_o$
410 profile has become almost linear, and the location of the peak has stabilized. From this time onwards, the
411 peak keeps rising together with the concentration in the CIZ until almost reaching a plateau by minute
412 30. A video with the evolution of the $[K^+]_o$ profile with time is available in the Supplementary Material
413 section (Movie SM1).

414 To test the sensitivity of the results to the time-course of $[ADP]_i$ and the spatial extension of the
415 pH transition zone, simulations considering the ADP time-course proposed by Weiss et al. (1992) were
416 performed for three different pH transition zone sizes (0 cm, 0.5 cm, and 1 cm). Results from the simulations
417 are shown in Fig S4 in the Supplementary Material. The results show that the ADP data from Weiss et al.
418 (1992) leads to a lower rate of rise of $[K^+]_o$ during the primary rising phase, which delays the potassium
419 plateau with respect to our control simulations based on the ADP data from Terkildsen et al. (2007).
420 However, the results are qualitatively similar. Indeed, a plateau is reached when AP alternans flatten the
421 curve, the same as in our main simulations (compare left and right curves in Fig S4 panels B and C).
422 As for the $[K^+]_o$ spatial profiles, they are affected by the time-course of ADP (the size of the $[K^+]_o$
423 border zone in particular), with changes in the order of a 10%, with the pH transition zone affecting less.
424 However, the time evolution described in the previous paragraphs is observed to be the same for both of the
425 considered ADP time-courses. Furthermore, simulations performed with a mesh size of 0.125 mm showed
426 no difference in the results with respect to those obtained with a mesh size of 0.25 mm (see Fig S5 in the
427 Supplementary Material).

428 Furthermore, to better understand the mechanisms behind the formation of the BZ, a sensitivity analysis
429 of the effect of the tissue conductivity and the potassium diffusion coefficient was performed. Together with
430 the control simulation, the following combination of parameters were considered: i) The tissue conductivity,
431 D_V , was reduced by 20%, by 60%, and by 80% down to 0.0005 mS (conduction velocity of 30 cm/s)
432 while keeping the extracellular potassium diffusion coefficient, D_K , at the control value in Table 1; ii)
433 the extracellular potassium diffusion coefficient, D_K , was multiplied by 0 (no extracellular potassium
434 transport i.e., $D_K = 0.0$), by 10, and by 100 while keeping the effective tissue conductivity to the value in
435 Table 1. Results of these simulations are shown in Fig S6 of the Supplementary Material, whereas Fig 6B
436 shows only results for four representative cases. Results show that increasing D_K reduces the value of
437 $[K^+]_o$ in the central ischemic zone and enlarges the BZ by increasing the region in the distal part of the
438 normoxic tissue affected by ischemia. This leads to a smoother transition between the normoxic and the
439 CIZ. Conversely, reducing D_V makes the BZ smaller, reduces the maximum $[K^+]_o$, and leads to a biphasic
440 $[K^+]_o$ spatial profile. The reduction in the maximum $[K^+]_o$ and the biphasic behavior in the spatial profile
441 are caused by an early appearance of AP alternans in the border zone and conduction block in the CIZ as
442 D_V decreases. The early appearance of AP alternans cause a premature ending of the rising phase, whereas
443 the absence of systolic current in the CIZ after conduction block causes a reduction in the extracellular

444 K^+ efflux responsible for the biphasic behavior in the spatial profile. Most importantly, results indicates a
445 larger influence of the electrotonic coupling compared to extracellular potassium transport in the formation
446 of the BZ. Indeed, the figure shows that a 60% reduction in tissue conductivity implies a 40% reduction in
447 the size of the BZ (from 1.2 cm to 0.72 cm), whereas a 10 fold increases in D_K only increased the size of
448 the BZ in a 10% (from 1.2 cm to 1.35 cm). In addition, the total suppression of extracellular potassium
449 transport left the BZ almost unaltered (see Fig 6B).

450 To better understand the role of extracellular potassium transport in the $[K^+]_o$ accumulation, the efflux,
451 influx and net efflux diffusion rates as a function of time are depicted in Fig 7 for two positions in the tissue,
452 namely $x = 2.5$ cm in the BZ, and $x = 3.5$ cm in the CIZ. The figure shows that the net diffusion efflux
453 rate is four orders of magnitude smaller than the net efflux associated with the various ion channels shown
454 in Fig 3. The figure also shows that net diffusion efflux rate results non-zero when the $[K^+]_o$ experiences a
455 maximum (see panel A and B in Fig 7), or during the transition from the first rising phase to the second
456 rising phase (see panels C and D in Fig 7). However, even in this case, the net diffusion efflux is much
457 smaller than the transmembrane efflux. From the analysis of Fig 7 it emerges that the evolution in the
458 spatial $[K^+]_o$ profile is associated with a heterogeneous local potassium accumulation in the altered region.

459 3.2.2 Electrophysiological manifestations of the extracellular potassium accumulation in tissue

460 Fig 8 shows the $[K^+]_o$ time profile at different locations within the tissue, together with the evolution of
461 the APs and the electrograms during the first 16 minutes of ischemia. The time profile of $[K^+]_o$ (Panel
462 A) changes according to the position within the tissue. While in the unaltered region the $[K^+]_o$ remains
463 constant, as expected, in the BZ (position $x = 2$ cm) the time profile shows a non monotonic behavior,
464 in good agreement with the experimental results reported by Coronel et al. (1988) in regionally ischemic
465 pig hearts. As moving from the BZ towards the center of the ischemic zone (positions $x = 2.9$ cm and
466 $x = 3.3$ cm), the $[K^+]_o$ time profile evolves toward the characteristic triphasic shape shown in Fig 2A for
467 the isolated cell, and in good agreement with experimental data reported by Hill and Gettes (1980). While
468 the local triphasic behavior of $[K^+]_o$ is associated with the ionic mechanisms described in the previous
469 sections, the heterogeneity in the $[K^+]_o$ time profile within the tissue appears to be mainly related to the
470 electrotonic coupling as demonstrated in Fig 6B.

471 The heterogeneity observed in the $[K^+]_o$ time profile is also observed in the APD (Fig 8B) and in the
472 APs themselves (Fig 8C). Within the CIZ ($x = 3.3$ cm) the AP shows changes in morphology associated
473 with the alterations due to ischemia, with alternans developing after the 2.5 minute mark, followed by
474 total loss of excitability after the 5.5 minute mark. Concomitant changes are observed in the proximal side
475 of the CIZ ($x = 2.9$ cm). Here, a certain degree of alternation is also observed, though the cells remain
476 electrically responsive during the whole simulation period. At the proximal side of the BZ ($x = 2.0$ cm),
477 AP alternans are hardly noticed and the only changes in the AP morphology happen due to alterations
478 associated with ischemia.

479 These electrophysiologic changes are clearly reflected in the electrograms depicted in Fig 8D for different
480 positions in the tissue. The electrograms show the typical depression in the ST segment due to ischemia in
481 the altered region (small black arrows in Fig 8D), whereas the alternans in the AP are reflected in alternans
482 in the T-wave (see Fig 8D right panel). The conduction block in the CIZ at minute 13 is evident by the total
483 suppression in of the T-wave in all electrograms, and the monophasic electrogram at the CIZ ($x = 3.3$ cm).

484 3.2.3 Injury current during acute regional ischemia

485 The hypothesis that during acute ischemia, a current flowing between the ischemic and the normal tissue,
486 a current of injury, may cause depolarization of the normal cells near the border zone has been proposed
487 in several studies (Janse et al., 1980; Coronel et al., 1991). To explore this hypothesis more in detail
488 by means of numerical simulations, the injury current in the tissue at 3 minutes and 4 minutes after the
489 onset of ischemia were computed. The upper panel in Fig 9 show the AP at three position in the tissue
490 located at the normal zone ($x = 0.9$ mm), the border zone ($x = 2.3$ mm), and the central ischemic zone
491 ($x = 3.2$ mm), whereas panel B shows the electrograms at the same positions. The instant t_A has been
492 chosen in correspondence with the end of repolarization of the cell in the normal zone, coincident with
493 the point of deep negative T wave in the electrogram recorded in the ischemic zone. On the contrary, t_B
494 corresponds to an instant of complete repolarization in the three positions. Panel C shows the depolarization
495 current density for the stimulations at 3 and 4 minutes after the onset of ischemia, at the instant when the
496 propagation front is entering the altered region ($x = 2$ cm). Panel D depicts the intracellular injury currents
497 at instants t_A and t_B at 3 minutes and 4 minutes after the onset of ischemia.

498 The results in Fig 9 show that the magnitude of the depolarization current, required to generate an ectopic
499 beat, is about eight times larger than the magnitude of the injury current flowing from the ischemic to the
500 normal zone.

4 DISCUSSION

501 4.1 Main findings

502 The main findings of our work can be summarized as follows:

- 503 1. Ischemia-induced extracellular potassium accumulation and its characteristic triphasic time course are
504 an intrinsic feature of the isolated ischemic cell (Fig 2). Though modulated by diffusion of potassium
505 within the tissue, they are not directly caused by it.
- 506 2. The primary (initial) rising phase of $[K^+]_o$ is mainly caused by a strong progressive reduction of
507 potassium influx (due to the partial inhibition of the NaK pump) concomitant with a lesser increase in
508 the efflux (due to enhancements in I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$).
- 509 3. The smooth transition to the plateau phase of $[K^+]_o$ is mainly caused by the appearance of electrical
510 AP alternans, which are in turn provoked by the combination of a lower cell excitability together with
511 an enhanced $I_{K(ATP)}$.
- 512 4. Once the alternating period is over, the plateau phase of $[K^+]_o$ is mainly caused by the predominantly
513 short APs that stabilize potassium efflux.
- 514 5. The secondary rise in $[K^+]_o$ is mainly caused by a stabilization of potassium efflux (due to enhanced
515 I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$) concomitant with a slower decrease in the magnitude of the influx carried by a
516 depressed NaK pump.
- 517 6. The results obtained in a regionally ischemic tissue explain the progressive appearance of a potassium
518 BZ of approximately 1.2 cm within the proximal end of the ischemic zone.
- 519 7. The simulations suggest that the $[K^+]_o$ spatial profile is mainly due to the electrotonic coupling that
520 modulates the ionic currents and the subsequent net potassium efflux, with the extracellular potassium
521 transport playing a minor role.

522 8. Results from the simulations suggest that the injury current associated with the deep negative T-wave
523 in the ischemic zone may not be sufficient to depolarize healthy cells in the normal zone. In addition,
524 part of the outward injury current occurs inside the altered tissue, where the cells are still within the
525 effective refractory period.

526 While findings 1, 2, 4, 6 and 8 confirm previous hypothesis and results from previous modeling works
527 regarding the extracellular K^+ accumulation during acute ischemia, findings 3, 4, 5 and 7 identify novel
528 mechanisms behind the time course of K^+ accumulation and its spatial heterogeneity during acute ischemia.
529 These findings are discussed in detail in the following sections.

530 4.2 Comparison with experimental data

531 The results obtained with our model show a very high degree of agreement with experimental data. This
532 applies both to the time course of $[K^+]_o$ and to the APD. As seen in Fig 2A, the time course of $[K^+]_o$
533 during the primary rise, the plateau and the initial phase of the secondary rise is quantitatively consistent
534 with experimental data from rabbit hearts subject to global acute ischemia (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995). As
535 shown in Fig S1 of the Supplementary Material, other experiments conducted in animal hearts also show
536 qualitative similarities with ours, both in globally ischemic hearts (Weiss and Shine, 1981, 1982b,a; Kléber
537 et al., 1987; Wilde et al., 1990) and in regionally ischemic hearts (Hill and Gettes, 1980; Hirche et al., 1980;
538 Friedrich et al., 1981; Watanabe and Gettes, 2016, 2018). Although the slope of rise in both phases and
539 the time to reach the plateau vary with species and experimental conditions, the qualitative resemblance
540 between experiments and our simulations stands out.

541 Experimental evidence shows that the rate of rise of $[K^+]_o$ depends on the frequency with which the
542 heart is stimulated (Weiss and Shine, 1982a, 1986; Weiss et al., 1989; Wilde and Aksnes, 1995; Kanda
543 et al., 1997). To test if our model correctly reproduced this dependency, we stimulated our virtual myocyte
544 at different frequencies and monitored the time course of $[K^+]_o$. The results, shown in Fig 2B, are in
545 qualitative agreement with the experimental results (Weiss and Shine, 1982a; Wilde and Aksnes, 1995). As
546 observed in experimental recordings, the model predicts a slower potassium rise at lower heart rates. In
547 particular, if the cell is not stimulated at all (0 beats per minute), the level of $[K^+]_o$ transiently and slightly
548 decreases below the normoxic value before eventually increasing, which is also found in the experiments
549 (see Fig 2 in (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995) and Fig 5 in (Weiss and Shine, 1982a)).

550 As for the evolution of the APD, data from the literature obtained in ischemic human hearts is scarce
551 because it is very difficult to obtain. The data from Sutton et al. (2000), plotted in Fig 5A (lower panel),
552 was recorded during 3 minutes from a single left ventricular epicardial site in patients undergoing coronary
553 artery surgery during cardiopulmonary bypass. To the best of our knowledge, they are the only available
554 MAP data for comparison purposes in human *in-vivo*. Our results are in very close agreement with these
555 data (see Fig 5A).

556 A very close agreement with experimental data is also found in the tissue simulations. Indeed, the
557 two middle panels of Fig 8A show a direct comparison of the time course of $[K^+]_o$ in two locations
558 (corresponding to the proximal and distal ends of the BZ - 2.0 cm and 2.9 cm, respectively) with
559 experimental data from Coronel et al. (1988) and Hill and Gettes (1980). The quantitative agreement is,
560 again, very notorious. It should be highlighted that all the mentioned experimental data were not used to
561 train or fit the model, and were not even considered when defining our ischemic cellular and tissue model.
562 The data on potassium accumulation and AP behaviour were only looked at *a posteriori* to test the validity

563 of the model. The good agreement between our results and the experiments demonstrates the goodness of
564 the computational model from a predictive point of view.

565 As for the time course of the net efflux rate resulting from our simulations, it is also in accordance
566 with experimental measurements in animals (Wilde et al., 1990). In this experiment, a rapid increase in
567 the net efflux rate, followed by a decrease to almost zero and an eventual slower increase, was found in
568 globally ischemic mammalian hearts. The values they obtained for the net efflux rate are in the range of our
569 simulated values.

570 Unfortunately, to our knowledge, the rise in $[K^+]_o$ in the acutely-ischemic human heart has not been
571 measured directly, so direct comparisons with our results cannot be made. In 1970, Parker et al. (1970)
572 measured potassium concentration in human and reported an increase during acute ischemia. Unfortunately,
573 they measured potassium concentration in the arterial flow but not in the myocardial interstitium. In
574 2014, Kazbanov et al. (2014) inferred the time course of $[K^+]_o$ in the *in-vivo* human ischemic heart
575 during 180 seconds using a very indirect methodology. Although their results cannot be regarded as actual
576 $[K^+]_o$ measurements, the triphasic trend they reported agrees with the results in animal and with our own
577 simulation results. Also, they report a calculated mean increase in $[K^+]_o$ of 2.2 mmol/L after 2.5 minutes,
578 which is in the range of our results (2.57 mmol/L, see Fig 2A).

579 As for the dispersion of $[K^+]_o$ during regional ischemia and size of the BZ, our model predicted a BZ
580 of about 1.2 cm at 10 minutes after occlusion (see Fig 6A). These results are in good agreement with the
581 work by Hill and Gettes (1980); Coronel et al. (1991) that reported a BZ of approximately 1 cm in acute
582 regional ischemia in isolated pig heart 7 minutes after occlusion. In addition, our model predicts that $[K^+]_o$
583 accumulates outside the BZ, in the normal zone, for a distance of about 2 mm, in close agreement with the
584 results from Coronel et al. (1991).

585 According to our simulations, the injury current during the negative T wave, corresponding to a potential
586 gradient of almost 60 mV across the BZ, (see Fig 9) was of $1.5 \mu A/mm^3$ at 3 minutes post-occlusion
587 and $2 \mu A/mm^3$ at 4 minutes post-occlusion. These values are found to be in good agreement with the 2
588 $\mu A/mm^3$ reported by Janse et al. (1980) in canine hearts at 4 minutes after LAD occlusion. Further, we
589 found that this current was about eight times smaller than the excitatory current provided by the traveling
590 front. This result is higher than the results from Janse et al. (1980) who reported an excitatory current as
591 twice as large as the injury current. However, they computed the current with electrodes spaced a distance
592 between 1.5 to 4 mm which lead to an underestimation of the excitatory current as demonstrated in Coronel
593 et al. (2000). On the contrary, the intracellular depolarizing current computed by our model at the metabolic
594 border was found to be in good agreement with the experiments from Coronel et al. (2000) on porcine
595 heart, and the simulation results from Potse et al. (2007a).

596 In summary, the good agreement between experimental evidences and the results obtained with our
597 model, both in the single cell and tissue levels, enables us to suggest new hypothesis regarding the intimate
598 mechanisms of ischemia-induced hyperkalemia, as will be explained in the next sections.

599 4.3 The mechanisms of extracellular potassium accumulation

600 Experimental evidence shows that extracellular potassium concentration in the interstitium of acutely
601 ischemic myocardial tissue shows a triphasic time pattern, with an initial rapid rise being followed
602 by a plateau phase and a secondary slower increase. Regardless of the intimate mechanisms involved,
603 dynamic changes in $[K^+]_o$ must be due to an imbalance between potassium efflux and influx to and from

604 cardiomyocytes. If the former is higher than the latter, $[K^+]_o$ will increase, and vice versa. Said triphasic
605 pattern is the result of the interplay between efflux and influx during the acute phase of ischemia.

606 4.3.1 Primary rising phase

607 Due to the difficulties related to the direct measurement of the individual contributions to the rapid
608 primary rise of $[K^+]_o$, the classical hypotheses that aim an explanation are basically of speculative nature.
609 In summary, the following factors have mainly been hypothesized to play a role: (a) a partial inhibition
610 of the NaK pump, (b) an enhancement of the $I_{K(ATP)}$ current, (c) an increase of sodium influx and (d) a
611 reduction of the interstitial volume. Also, the discussion as to whether the extent to which this rise is due to
612 an increased efflux and/or a reduced influx is still not resolved (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995; Weiss et al., 2017)

613 Regarding the partial inhibition of the NaK pump, due to the decrease in the intracellular ATP/ADP
614 ratio, this effect is included in our model. Indeed, the last row in Fig 4 shows the decrease in magnitude of
615 the current carried by the pump. Moreover, the bars in Fig 3 (and also the results shown in Fig S3 of the
616 Supplementary Material) show that the magnitude of the influx rate through the pump rapidly decreases
617 during the primary rising phase of $[K^+]_o$, with the decrease in the magnitude of the potassium influx rate
618 seen in Fig 2C being the direct consequence of this partial inhibition. Indeed, our results clearly show that
619 this reduction is pivotal in explaining the primary rise in $[K^+]_o$, because the reduction in the influx (55% in
620 2.5 minutes), almost exclusively generated by the NaK pump depression, is much higher than the increase
621 in the efflux during this phase (10% in 2.5 minutes). This confirms the experimentally derived hypothesis
622 regarding the importance of the NaK pump inhibition. Also, this is in accordance with the main conclusion
623 of a previous modelling study (Terkildsen et al., 2007). According to their model, the inhibition of the NaK
624 pump is the major driving force for potassium loss. This is difficult to correlate with experimental findings
625 because quantification of the influx rate of the NaK pump relies on indirect methods (Wilde and Aksnes,
626 1995). Yet, evidence of an ischemia-induced depression of the pump exists (Bersohn et al., 1982; Mitani
627 and Shattock, 1992).

628 Regarding the enhancement of the ATP-sensitive potassium current, Our results show that, indeed, this
629 factor is not as essential as the depression of the NaK pump in the primary rise of $[K^+]_o$. On the one
630 hand, the efflux rate increase related to the enhancement of $I_{K(ATP)}$ 5 minutes post-occlusion is only
631 5.8 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s (see Fig 3D and Fig S3 of the Supplementary Material), which is much smaller than the
632 concomitant influx rate decrease (20 ($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s). In that same time period, the increase in the efflux rate
633 provoked by the increase in I_{K1} , for instance, is 5.6($\mu\text{mol/L}$)/s, almost equal to the $I_{K(ATP)}$ case. The lack
634 of a higher increase in the $I_{K(ATP)}$ -related efflux seems to be paradoxical with the continuous increase in
635 the peak value of the current shown in the third row of Fig 4. The explanation, also pointed out by Wilde
636 and Aksnes (1995) and Weiss et al. (2017), is that the $I_{K(ATP)}$ increase is a self-limiting mechanism in
637 terms of potassium efflux, because the continue increase in its peak is counteracted by the decrease in its
638 duration caused by the continuous reduction in APD_{90} . Thus, our results show that $I_{K(ATP)}$ does play a
639 role in the primary potassium accumulation phase, but it is quantitatively less important than other currents
640 (mainly the NaK pump).

641 Regarding the modification in sodium influx and its role in the primary phase of potassium accumulation,
642 the classical hypothesis is that the increase in potassium efflux is a passive consequence of an increased
643 sodium influx to maintain electroneutrality (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995; Shivkumar et al., 1997). Further,
644 there is evidence that $[Na^+]_i$ increases during acute ischemia (see Wilde and Aksnes (1995) for a review),
645 although the exact extent is unknown. $[Na^+]_i$ does indeed increase in our simulations (from 7.3 mmol/L in
646 normoxia to 9.3 mmol/L in 5 minutes, as seen in Fig S7). Although we did not analyze the causes of this

647 increase, the partial inhibition of the NaK pump seems to be the main factor responsible. This increase in
648 intracellular sodium is necessarily coupled to the increase in extracellular potassium (Wilde and Aksnes,
649 1995; Shivkumar et al., 1997). According to our results, however, the change of one of them is not the
650 driving cause of the other, but rather they are both caused by their common underlying mechanism: the
651 reduction of the NaK pump itself. As pointed out in Terkildsen et al. (2007), the partial inhibition of the
652 pump accounts for both concentration changes.

653 Finally, a shrinkage of the interstitial extracellular space provoked by the ischemia-induced alteration of
654 osmotic pressure has also been hypothesized to play a role in the increase in $[K^+]_o$ (Wilde and Aksnes,
655 1995). We preferred not to include this mechanism in our main set of simulations due to its intrinsically
656 different nature compared to the efflux-influx interplay. However, we conducted separate simulations to
657 assess the quantitative importance of the extracellular volume regulation. The main result is shown in Fig S8
658 of the Supplementary Material, where we compare the basic “control” simulation of Fig 2A with a situation
659 in which extracellular volume was reduced by 9% in 30 minutes (data extrapolated from Terkildsen et al.
660 (2007)). The curves show that the effect of extracellular shrinkage was almost negligible during the primary
661 $[K^+]_o$ rising phase, and its effects were only notorious (but very limited) in the long term. Indeed, the
662 contribution of the extracellular volume reduction was only +0.6 mmol/L after 20 minutes. These results are
663 quantitatively similar to a previous modeling study (Terkildsen et al., 2007) and experimental results (Yan
664 et al., 1996).

665 4.3.2 Transition to the potassium plateau

666 One of the most intriguing and novel result from our simulations refers to the causes of the smooth
667 transition to the extracellular potassium plateau and its relationship with AP alternans. As explained in the
668 Results section, the model predicts the appearance of electrical alternans between the fourth and the sixth
669 minute of ischemia in the isolated cell model (Fig 5B and E). Moreover, the tissue simulations also show
670 AP alternans in the distal altered zone (Fig 8B). This is in correspondence with experimental results in
671 animals. Indeed, these type of alternans, occurring at normal/low stimulation frequencies (1 Hz in our case)
672 around 5 minutes post-occlusion (or even earlier), are a well-known feature of acute ischemia and have been
673 observed in AP or MAP recordings and/or in electrograms (Kléber et al., 1978; Nakashima et al., 1978;
674 Janse, 1990; Martišienė et al., 2015; Watanabe and Gettes, 2016). Moreover, the experimentally-obtained
675 waveforms of the alternating APs are very similar to our simulated results shown in Fig 5B. The “long” AP
676 has the upstroke divided in two phases, whereas the “short” one lacks the secondary phase. These exact
677 features were found in the APs directly recorded in pig hearts 5 minutes after clamping the LAD coronary
678 artery in pig hearts (see Fig 2 in Kléber et al. (1978) and Fig 4 in Janse (1990)). The morphology of the
679 AP alternans seen in Fig 1 in Downar et al. (1977) are very similar to those found in our tissue simulations
680 (Fig 8).

681 In our “0D simulations” (isolated cell), the onset of the $[K^+]_o$ plateau coincides with the alternans
682 phase (Fig 5E). Similarly, in our “1D simulations” (heterogeneous tissue), the alternating period is also
683 simultaneous with ($x=3.3\text{cm}$ in Fig 8) or precedes ($x=2.0\text{cm}$ and $x=2.9\text{cm}$ in Fig 8) the onset of the plateau.
684 In view of this result, we hypothesize that AP alternans are the main cause of the stabilization in the $[K^+]_o$
685 rise. To confirm this hypothesis, we conducted a separate simulation in which the alternans were inhibited
686 by artificially enhancing the I_{CaL} current at critical instants of the simulation in which the alternans were
687 just about to appear. The results, shown in Fig S9 of the Supplementary Material, indicate that the absence
688 of AP alternans abolishes the potassium plateau.

689 According to our simulations, the flattening of the $[K^+]_o$ curve occurs mainly because of a drastic
690 reduction in potassium efflux rate (see Fig 2C) caused by the AP alternans. Comparing Panels C and D
691 from Fig 3, indicates that this reduction is mostly due to the depression of the efflux carried by I_{Kr} and,
692 to a lesser extent, by I_{Kb} . These currents are active during the AP plateau (i.e. during systole). When
693 alternans appear, the duration of the plateau is reduced at least in one of every two APs, which provokes
694 a reduction in the potassium carried by said currents. This reduces potassium efflux and decelerates the
695 “macro” $[K^+]_o$ curve (Fig 5A) due to the behaviour of the “micro” $[K^+]_o$ fluctuations (Fig 5E).

696 Different experimental results have been published in which APD and $[K^+]_o$ (or potassium activity) are
697 measured simultaneously during no-flow acute ischemia (Weiss and Shine, 1982b, 1986; Weiss et al., 1992;
698 Kléber, 1983). In one case (Weiss et al., 1992), the potassium plateau was not reached during the duration
699 of the experiment. In another (Weiss and Shine, 1982b), the existence of electrical alternans cannot be
700 inferred (see their Fig 2). This could be due to the low resolution with which they measure APD (one
701 measurement per minute), which makes it impossible to detect short periods of AP alternation. However,
702 in one publication (Kléber, 1983), APD is measured with enough resolution as to detect alternans. In their
703 Fig 2A, alternans are found between 4.5 and 5.5 minutes post-occlusion, just as in our case. The alternans
704 occurred before the onset of the extracellular potassium plateau. In our “1D simulations” (heterogeneous
705 tissue), similar results have been found. Moreover, Watanabe and Gettes (2016) found AP alternans in pig
706 hearts subject to regional ischemia before and during the plateau phase (see their Fig 5).

707 The mechanisms that give rise to the $[K^+]_o$ plateau phase are not yet clarified. According to Weiss and
708 Shine (1986), the reduction of APD as ischemia progresses contributes to the existence of the plateau.
709 They found that the onset of the plateau occurred when APD had reduced to about two thirds. In our
710 “0D simulations”, that was the case when the curve begins to flatten just when the alternans began to
711 appear: the APD_{90} value transitioned from its normoxic value of 289 milliseconds to 192 milliseconds
712 just before the onset of alternans, which corresponds to a 66% percentage reduction of the control value.
713 They hypothesized that the decrease in APD reduced the potassium efflux rate until it equaled the influx
714 rate, giving rise to the plateau. This is consistent with our results (Fig 2C and Fig 5).

715 Indeed, in our “0D simulations”, the net potassium efflux rate is almost zero in the plateau around the
716 10 minute mark. It stays below $2.2 (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$ (10% of its peak value) from the 6.8 to the 13.4 minute
717 mark. During this period, influx and efflux rates are almost balanced with a value of $\approx 10 (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$,
718 which is much smaller than in normoxia ($\approx 34.5 (\mu\text{mol/L})/\text{s}$). On the one hand, influx rate is smaller
719 than in normoxia because of the progressive partial inhibition of the NaK pump. On the other hand,
720 efflux rate is also smaller due to the short duration of the AP plateau, which practically eliminates all
721 potassium currents except for I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$. The former is not AP plateau-dependent (due to its inward
722 rectification nature), while the latter has a high peak due to the low value of the ATP/ADP ratio at this point
723 in time. The overall result is a new stable $[K^+]_o$ at $\approx 11.7 \text{ mmol/L}$, the value up to which the initial 6.8
724 minutes lifted extracellular potassium. This can be better understood when comparing the “micro” $[K^+]_o$
725 fluctuations in Panels C and F from Fig 5: while both correspond to stable situations (normoxia in Panel C,
726 potassium plateau in panel F), the smaller fluctuations in the latter case are the consequence of smaller (but
727 approximately equal) efflux and influx compared to the normoxic case.

728 A further proof of the influence on APD on the plateau phase is given in Fig S9 of the Supplementary
729 Material. As explained above, artificial interventions were made to eliminate AP alternans. The lack of a
730 plateau phase in this separate simulation is because such interventions did not only abolish alternans but
731 also maintained APD_{90} levels high compared to the control simulation.

732 Another classical explanation of the potassium plateau, different to considerations on APD, is related to
733 the behaviour of the NaK pump. This has been argued both from experimental observations (see Wilde and
734 Aksnes (1995) for a review) and from previous computational modeling studies (Rodríguez et al., 2002;
735 Terkildsen et al., 2007). Simulations carried out by Terkildsen et al. (2007) showed that the time course of
736 I_{NaK} is triphasic and, according to them, the $[K^+]_o$ plateau is a reflection of the plateau in the activity of
737 the NaK pump, which, in turn, is due to the biphasic nature of the time course of intracellular ADP. In our
738 simulations, we also found a deceleration in the decrease of the magnitude of the NaK-related potassium
739 influx (see the bars in Fig 3 and also Fig S3 of the Supplementary Material) which was concomitant to the
740 potassium plateau, but the elimination of the alternans (Fig S9), while maintaining the NaK pump plateau,
741 abolished the potassium plateau. It must be noted that the model used by Terkildsen et al. is different
742 from ours, as it corresponds to the previous generation of AP models (Luo and Rudy, 1994) and is not as
743 comprehensive as the model used in this study (O'Hara et al., 2011). Also, their model of ischemia is
744 also less comprehensive. Using a similar AP and ischemia model, Rodríguez et al. (2002) explained the
745 plateau by the combined effect of the above discussed self-limiting effect of the activation of $I_{K(ATP)}$ and
746 an enhancement of the NaK pump which was not found with our model. In the model used by Rodríguez et
747 al., this enhancement was due to the regulatory effect exerted by the increase in both $[K^+]_o$ and $[Na^+]_i$
748 on the pump activity. Although this regulatory effect was included in our formulation of the NaK pump
749 following Cortassa et al. (2006) and Terkildsen et al. (2007), its effect was more modest than in the former
750 model. Our model is consistent with the fact that the increase produced by $[K^+]_o$ elevation between 4
751 and 12 mmol/L is mild (Gadsby, 1980; Glitsch et al., 1981; Weiss and Shine, 1986) and surpassed by the
752 opposite effect caused by the decrease in the intracellular ATP/ADP ratio.

753 4.3.3 Secondary rising phase

754 The prior hypotheses regarding the causes of the secondary slower rise in potassium accumulation are
755 scarce. Classically, this phase has been related to cell irreversible damage (Weiss and Shine, 1982b). It
756 is not completely clear if the cause is related to an increase in potassium efflux provoked by the loss of
757 sarcolemmal integrity or by a further depletion of NaK pump activity (Weiss and Shine, 1986). According
758 to a previous modeling study, the latter could be the main cause (Terkildsen et al., 2007). From our results,
759 a complementary hypothesis may be established. Cell membrane damage was not included in our model, so
760 our results discard the relevance of this factor. According to our simulations, potassium efflux rate almost
761 plateaus during the secondary rise in $[K^+]_o$ while the magnitude of the influx keeps decreasing, giving rise
762 to a secondary increase in the net potassium efflux rate (see Fig 2C). The fact that the efflux is maintained
763 is mainly due to plateauing of both I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$ (see the bars in Fig 3, the ionic currents in Fig 4 and
764 also Fig S3 of the Supplementary Material). As for the secondary decrease in the influx rate, it is due to
765 the secondary depression of the NaK pump (see the same figures), which is consistent with the fact that
766 intracellular ATP levels keep decreasing, though at a smaller rate compared to the primary phase (Fig 1).

767 This phenomenon may be alternatively explained from a different perspective. The rate of rise in the
768 secondary $[K^+]_o$ increase (from ≈ 14 minutes onwards, see Fig 2A) is in the same order of magnitude as
769 the primary rise when the cell is quiescent (lower curve in Fig 2B). This can also be seen in experimental
770 results (e.g. Wilde and Aksnes (1995), Fig 1). The reason is that both situations are very similar in terms of
771 the electrical activity. On the one hand, in the quiescent case, there are no APs, so the efflux and influx
772 completely depends on the diastolic currents. On the other hand, in the secondary rise when pacing, the
773 isolated cell (Fig 4, last row at the 20 minute mark) and the ischemic tissue (Fig 8, last row at the 13 minute
774 mark) are unresponsive, having lost excitability due to the high $[K^+]_o$ value.

775 4.3.4 The potassium border zone

776 The potassium gradient that is established during acute regional ischemia near the metabolic border,
777 the BZ, is believed to be related with the extracellular potassium transport (Coronel et al., 1988, 1989).
778 However, our simulations indicate the size of the BZ to be related to the electrotonic coupling between
779 cells close to the metabolic border, with a minor role of the extracellular potassium transport in modulating
780 the BZ (see Fig 6B). Our results indicate that, an effective modulation of the BZ by potassium transport
781 requires a ten-fold increase in the potassium diffusion coefficient (see Fig 6B). These findings are in
782 agreement with the work from Potse et al. (2007b) who conclude that the mechanism that leads to a smooth
783 distribution of $[K^+]_o$ cannot be physical diffusion alone. They suggest pulsating flow in the arterial and
784 venous bed as possibly responsible for the increase in the potassium diffusion coefficient, a hypothesis also
785 proposed by Janse and Wit (1989). However, it is retained very unlikely that pulsating flow can increase
786 the effective diffusion coefficient ten times with respect the measured diffusion constant of potassium
787 in water, as to be able to sustain the smooth distribution of extracellular potassium observed in acute
788 ischemia. However, the results in Fig 7, panels B and D, indicate a transport of potassium from the ischemic
789 toward the normal myocardium where the excess of potassium is removed by the washout. Our results
790 clearly evidenced the need of systolic currents i.e., a propagating front in the tissue, for the development
791 of the BZ. In fact, considering only diastolic currents as in the work by Niederer (2013) leads to a BZ
792 of only few millimeters wide and a limited rise of the extracellular potassium. Considering a BZ equally
793 ischemic, the mechanism revealed by our model says that electrotonic coupling modifies the net potassium
794 efflux in the BZ by modulating the current through ionic channels responsible for potassium efflux, with
795 cellular potassium loss being similar in closely adjacent cells. This explains the small invasion of ischemic
796 conditions within the healthy metabolic area, limited by the presence of potassium washout in the unaltered
797 tissue. Moving into the ischemic zone, the effect of the metabolic border reduces until reaching a situation
798 like what is seen in an isolated cell. In this regard, enhancing potassium diffusion makes this transition
799 smoother as shown in Fig 6B.

800

801 4.4 Limitations of the study

802 Our study presents several potential limitations. The first one is that the simulation of progressive acute
803 ischemia relies on the chosen time courses of the ischemic parameters which are imposed to the model
804 (see Fig 1A-D). They have been taken from experimental measurements or calculations reported in the
805 literature (Sakamoto et al., 2000; Weiss et al., 1992; Terkildsen et al., 2007; Daleau, 1999; Gautier et al.,
806 2008). None of them correspond to measurements in human hearts (due to the lack of data) but rather
807 belong to different species (guinea-pig and rabbit) and were obtained in different laboratories and contexts.
808 However, our additional simulations shown in Figs S1 and S3 of the Supplementary Material, as already
809 discussed, indicate that the results obtained with different ischemic parameter time courses are qualitatively
810 similar, so the main conclusions of our study are not hampered by this potential limitation.

811 Another potential limitation is related to the fact that our results have been obtained with a particular AP
812 model (O'Hara et al. (2011)), so the results may be model-dependent. We preferred to use the model by
813 O'Hara et al. because it has been widely used in the past decade and it was adopted by an expert group of
814 the Federal Drug administration (FDA) as the starting point for developing an *in-silico* model suitable for
815 regulatory decision making (Colatsky et al., 2016). However, to assess the impact on the chosen model on
816 the results, we carried out another separate simulation using the more recent human ventricular cell AP
817 model by Tomek et al. (2019). The result is shown in Fig S10 of the Supplementary Material. Again, the

818 results with both models are very similar and our main conclusions regarding the potassium triphasic time
819 course and the mechanisms responsible for the plateau are still valid.

820 Our tissue simulations have been performed with a 1D model, which may represent a limitation since the
821 effect of electrotonic coupling is enhanced with spatial dimensionality. However, if the stimulation consists
822 in a planar wave in 2D or 3D this effect is greatly reduced and differences in the results between 1D, 2D
823 or 3D simulations are small. In this regard, our future work will simulate 30 minutes of dynamic acute
824 ischemia in a real 3D geometry of a biventricular heart considering electrophysiological variability and
825 tissue structure. We hope, in this case to reproduce a realistic border zone, but most importantly, this new
826 set of simulations may provide further insights about the importance of electrotonic coupling in $[K^+]_o$
827 accumulation during acute regional ischemia.

828 One of the main limitations of the study is that our model does not consider the mechano-sensitivity of
829 K(ATP) channels (Van Wagoner, 1993; Kohl et al., 2006; Peyronnet et al., 2016; Quinn and Kohl, 2021).
830 Taking into account that stretch modulates the channel sensitivity to ATP and ADP, this could lead to further
831 shortening of the AP duration and in turn this could affect the results regarding extracellular potassium
832 accumulation and the formation of the BZ. Some models in the literature have considered this effect (e.g.
833 (Li et al., 2006)) by simply scaling the maximum conductance of K(ATP) channels to account for stretch.
834 We chose not to do so due to the lack of data regarding the stretch levels in the CIZ and the BZ. However,
835 we acknowledge that this could affect the main results of this work. For instance, our main findings 1 and
836 2 could be hampered by the lack of mechano-electric feedback in the model. Further simulations with a
837 model that includes the mechano-sensitivity of K(ATP) channels, as well as other stretch-activated non
838 specific channels, would be needed to assess its impact on the results, which could be related to possible
839 depolarizing effects in the BZ that could eventually lead to triggered activity. However, such simulations
840 were beyond the scope of the present work.

841 Moreover, the cellular ischemic model lacks a description of the effect of other ischemia-related
842 parameters, such as catecholamines, adenosine, fatty acid metabolites, etc, which could affect the
843 outcome of the model. Also, the tissue model was one-dimensional and represented an electrophysiology
844 homogeneous (though metabolically heterogeneous) cardiac strand. While it was useful to study the effects
845 of regional ischemia on extracellular potassium accumulation, it lacks a proper anatomical and structural
846 description of realistic three-dimensional ventricles. In particular, transmural and apex-to-base differences
847 in APs, as well as anisotropy, could not be included in the model. Finally, inter-subject variability was not
848 considered in our study. To do so, a set of population models should be carried out in which some relevant
849 parameters (e.g. maximum conductances of ionic currents) were randomly varied within predetermined
850 ranges. Our results thus correspond to an “average” cell and tissue.

5 CONCLUSION

851 A model of cardiac tissue electrophysiology to investigate the spatio-temporal evolution of $[K^+]_o$ across
852 the ischemic BZ was developed. Our main results suggest that ischemia-related extracellular potassium
853 accumulation obeys to intrinsic features of the isolated ischemic cell. The characteristic triphasic time
854 course of $[K^+]_o$ is related to changes in the balance between the potassium influx and efflux. In this regard,
855 the initial rising phase of $[K^+]_o$ is mainly caused by a progressive reduction of potassium influx concomitant
856 with a lesser increase in the efflux, whereas the plateau phase is mainly initiated by the appearance of
857 electrical AP alternans provoked by a reduction in excitability together with an increase in $I_{K(ATP)}$ due to
858 the reduction in the intracellular ATP/ADP ratio. Finally, the secondary $[K^+]_o$ rising phase is associated
859 with an increment of the potassium efflux due to enhancement of I_{K1} and $I_{K(ATP)}$ and a reduction of the

860 NaK pump activity. Modulation of these mechanisms by electrotonic coupling is responsible for the spatial
861 distribution of $[K^+]_o$ and the formation of the ischemic BZ, with extracellular potassium transport having
862 a small influence. However, $[K^+]_o$ transport plays a major role in the stabilization of $[K^+]_o$ within the CIZ
863 when the tissue becomes non-excitable. The injury current associated with the deep negative T-wave in the
864 ischemic zone is found to be insufficient to depolarize healthy cells in the normal zone. In addition, part
865 of the outward injury current occur inside the altered tissue where the cells are still within the effective
866 refractory period.

6 CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

867 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
868 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

869 JFRM and JMF conceived and designed the study. Computational simulations were performed by
870 JFRM, JMF and AGA. The analysis/interpretation of the results was performed by JFRM and JMF,
871 with contributions of AGA. JFRM and JMF contributed to draft the manuscript, and all authors revised and
872 approved the submitted version.

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REFERENCES

- 882 Allen, D. G. and Orchard, C. H. (1987). Myocardial contractile function during ischemia and hypoxia.
883 *Circulation Research* 60, 153–168. doi:10.1161/01.RES.60.2.153
- 884 Babenko, A. P., Gonzalez, G., Aguilar-Bryan, L., and Bryan, J. (1998). Reconstituted human cardiac
885 K_{ATP} channels. *Circulation Research* 83, 1132–1143. doi:10.1161/01.RES.83.11.1132
- 886 Befroy, D. E., Powell, T., Radda, G. K., and Clarke, K. (1999). Osmotic shock: modulation of contractile
887 function, ϕ , and ischemic damage in perfused guinea pig heart. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart
888 and Circulatory Physiology* 276, H1236–H1244. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1999.276.4.H1236. PMID:
889 10199848

- 890 Bersohn, M. M., Philipson, K. D., and Fukushima, J. Y. (1982). Sodium-calcium exchange and sarcolemmal
891 enzymes in ischemic rabbit hearts. *American Journal of Physiology-Cell Physiology* 242, C288–C295.
892 doi:10.1152/ajpcell.1982.242.5.C288
- 893 Cao, F., Zervou, S., and Lygate, C. A. (2018). The creatine kinase system as a therapeutic target for
894 myocardial ischaemia–reperfusion injury. *Biochemical Society Transactions* 46, 1119–1127. doi:10.
895 1042/BST20170504
- 896 Carpio, E. F., Gomez, J. F., Rodríguez-Matas, J. F., Trenor, B., and Ferrero, J. M. (2022). Analysis of
897 vulnerability to reentry in acute myocardial ischemia using a realistic human heart model. *Computers in*
898 *Biology and Medicine* 141, 105038. doi:10.1016/j.compbiomed.2021.105038
- 899 Carpio, E. F., Gomez, J. F., Sebastian, R., Lopez-Perez, A., Castellanos, E., Almendral, J., et al. (2019).
900 Optimization of lead placement in the right ventricle during cardiac resynchronization therapy. a
901 simulation study. *Frontiers in Physiology* 10. doi:10.3389/fphys.2019.00074
- 902 Cascio, W. E., Yang, H., Muller-Borer, B. J., and Johnson, T. A. (2005). Ischemia-induced arrhythmia:
903 the role of connexins, gap junctions, and attendant changes in impulse propagation. *Journal of*
904 *Electrocardiology* 38, 55–59. doi:10.1016/j.jelectrocard.2005.06.019
- 905 Colatsky, T., Fermini, B., Gintant, G., Pierson, J. B., Sager, P., Sekino, Y., et al. (2016). The comprehensive
906 in vitro proarrhythmia assay (cipa) initiative — update on progress. *Journal of Pharmacological and*
907 *Toxicological Methods* 81, 15–20. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vascn.2016.06.002
- 908 Coronel, R. (1994). Heterogeneity in extracellular potassium concentration during early myocardial
909 ischaemia and reperfusion: implications for arrhythmogenesis. *Cardiovascular Research* 28, 770–777.
910 doi:10.1093/cvr/28.6.770
- 911 Coronel, R., Fiolet, J. W., Wilms-Schopman, F. J., Schaapherder, A. F., Johnson, T. A., Gettes, L. S.,
912 et al. (1988). Distribution of extracellular potassium and its relation to electrophysiologic changes
913 during acute myocardial ischemia in the isolated perfused porcine heart. *Circulation* 77, 1125–1138.
914 doi:10.1161/01.CIR.77.5.1125
- 915 Coronel, R., Fiolet, J. W., Wilms-Schopman, J. G., Opthof, T., Schaapherder, A. F., and Janse, M. J.
916 (1989). Distribution of extracellular potassium and electrophysiologic changes during two-stage coronary
917 ligation in the isolated, perfused canine heart. *Circulation* 80, 165–177. doi:10.1161/01.CIR.80.1.165
- 918 Coronel, R., Wilms-Schopman, F. J., DE Groot, J. R., Janse, M. J., Van Capelle, F. J., and DE Bakker,
919 J. M. (2000). Laplacian electrograms and the interpretation of complex ventricular activation patterns
920 during ventricular fibrillation. *Journal of Cardiovascular Electrophysiology* 11, 1119–1128. doi:10.
921 1111/j.1540-8167.2000.tb01758.x
- 922 Coronel, R., Wilms-Schopman, F. J., Opthof, T., van Capelle, F. J., and Janse, M. J. (1991). Injury current
923 and gradients of diastolic stimulation threshold, tq potential, and extracellular potassium concentration
924 during acute regional ischemia in the isolated perfused pig heart. *Circulation Research* 68, 1241–1249.
925 doi:10.1161/01.RES.68.5.1241
- 926 Cortassa, S., Aon, M. A., O'Rourke, B., Jacques, R., Tseng, H.-J., Marbán, E., et al. (2006). A
927 computational model integrating electrophysiology, contraction, and mitochondrial bioenergetics in the
928 ventricular myocyte. *Biophysical Journal* 91, 1564–1589. doi:10.1529/biophysj.105.076174
- 929 Daleau, P. (1999). Lysophosphatidylcholine, a metabolite which accumulates early in myocardium during
930 ischemia, reduces gap junctional coupling in cardiac cells. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology*
931 31, 1391–1401. doi:10.1006/jmcc.1999.0973
- 932 Doering, A. E., Eisner, D. A., and Lederer, W. J. (1996). Cardiac Na – Ca exchange and pH. *Annals of*
933 *the New York Academy of Sciences* 779, 182–198. doi:10.1111/j.1749-6632.1996.tb44786.x

- 934 Downar, E., Janse, M. J., and Durrer, D. (1977). The effect of acute coronary artery occlusion on
935 subepicardial transmembrane potentials in the intact porcine heart. *Circulation* 56, 217–224. doi:10.
936 1161/01.CIR.56.2.217
- 937 Dutta, S., Mincholé, A., Quinn, T. A., and Rodriguez, B. (2017). Electrophysiological properties of
938 computational human ventricular cell action potential models under acute ischemic conditions. *Progress*
939 *in Biophysics and Molecular Biology* 129, 40–52. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pbiomolbio.2017.02.007.
940 Validation of Computer Modelling
- 941 Egger, M. and Niggli, E. (2000). Paradoxical block of the $\text{Na}^+ - \text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger by extracellular protons
942 in guinea-pig ventricular myocytes. *The Journal of Physiology* 523, 353–366. doi:10.1111/j.1469-7793.
943 2000.t01-1-00353.x
- 944 Ferrero, J., Trenor, B., Saiz, J., Montilla, F., and Hernandez, V. (2003). Electrical activity and reentry in
945 acute regional ischemia: insights from simulations. In *Proceedings of the 25th Annual International*
946 *Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (IEEE Cat. No.03CH37439)*.
947 vol. 1, 17–20 Vol.1. doi:10.1109/IEMBS.2003.1279483
- 948 Ferrero, J. M., Sáiz, J., Ferrero, J. M., and Thakor, N. V. (1996). Simulation of action potentials from
949 metabolically impaired cardiac myocytes. *Circulation Research* 79, 208–221. doi:10.1161/01.RES.79.2.
950 208
- 951 Friedrich, R., Hirche, H., Keibel, U., Zylka, V., and Bissig, R. (1981). Changes of extracellular Na^+ ,
952 K^+ , Ca^{2+} and H^+ of the ischemic myocardium in pigs. *Basic Research in Cardiology* 76, 453–456.
953 doi:10.1007/BF01908341
- 954 Friedrich, T., Bamberg, E., and Nagel, G. (1996). Na^+ , $\text{K}^+ - \text{ATPase}$ pump currents in giant excised
955 patches activated by an atp concentration jump. *Biophysical Journal* 71, 2486–2500. doi:10.1016/
956 S0006-3495(96)79442-0
- 957 Gadsby, D. C. (1980). Activation of electrogenic $\text{Na}^+ \text{K}^+$ exchange by extracellular K^+ in canine cardiac
958 purkinje fibers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 77, 4035–4039. doi:10.1073/pnas.77.
959 7.4035
- 960 Gautier, M., Zhang, H., and Fearon, I. M. (2008). Peroxynitrite formation mediates lpc-induced
961 augmentation of cardiac late sodium currents. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 44,
962 241–251. doi:10.1016/j.yjmcc.2007.09.007
- 963 Glitsch, H. G., Kampmann, W., and Pusch, H. (1981). Activation of active na transport in sheep purkinje
964 fibres by external K or Rb ions. *Pflügers Archiv* 391, 28–34. doi:10.1007/BF00580690
- 965 Harper, J. R., Johnston, T. A., Engle, C. L., Martin, D. G., Eleet, W., and Gettes, L. S. (1993). Effect of rate
966 on changes in conduction velocity and extracellular potassium concentration during acute ischemia in
967 the in situ pig heart. *Journal of Cardiovascular Electrophysiology* 4, 661–671. doi:10.1111/j.1540-8167.
968 1993.tb01252.x
- 969 Harris, A. S., Bisteni, A., Russell, R. A., Brigham, J. C., and Firestone, J. E. (1954). Excitatory factors in
970 ventricular tachycardia resulting from myocardial ischemia. potassium a major excitant. *Science* 119,
971 200–203. doi:10.1126/science.119.3085.200
- 972 Hill, J. L. and Gettes, L. S. (1980). Effect of acute coronary artery occlusion on local myocardial
973 extracellular k^+ activity in swine. *Circulation* 61, 768–778. doi:10.1161/01.CIR.61.4.768
- 974 Hirche, H., Franz, C., Bös, L., Bissig, R., Lang, R., and Schramm, M. (1980). Myocardial extracellular
975 K^+ and H^+ increase and noradrenaline release as possible cause of early arrhythmias following acute
976 coronary artery occlusion in pigs. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 12, 579–593. doi:10.
977 1016/0022-2828(80)90016-4

- 978 Hotokebuchi, N., Yano, T., Nishizono, Y., and Nishi, K. (1987). Changes in intra- and extracellular
979 potassium and intracellular sodium activities induced by repetitive stimulation and their relation to
980 membrane potential in guinea-pig papillary muscle. *The Japanese Journal of Physiology* 37, 797–819.
981 doi:10.2170/jjphysiol.37.797
- 982 Janse, M. J. (1990). *Electrical activity immediately following myocardial infarction* (New York: Futura).
983 739–753
- 984 Janse, M. J. and Kléber, A. G. (1981). Electrophysiological changes and ventricular arrhythmias in the
985 early phase of regional myocardial ischemia. *Circulation Research* 49, 1069–1081. doi:10.1161/01.RES.
986 49.5.1069
- 987 Janse, M. J. and van Capelle, F. J. (1982). Electrotonic interactions across an inexcitable region as a cause
988 of ectopic activity in acute regional myocardial ischemia. a study in intact porcine and canine hearts and
989 computer models. *Circulation Research* 50, 527–537. doi:10.1161/01.RES.50.4.527
- 990 Janse, M. J., van Capelle, F. J., Morsink, H., Kléber, A. G., Wilms-Schopman, F., Cardinal, R., et al. (1980).
991 Flow of "injury" current and patterns of excitation during early ventricular arrhythmias in acute regional
992 myocardial ischemia in isolated porcine and canine hearts. evidence for two different arrhythmogenic
993 mechanisms. *Circulation Research* 47, 151–165. doi:10.1161/01.RES.47.2.151
- 994 Janse, M. J. and Wit, A. L. (1989). Electrophysiological mechanisms of ventricular arrhythmias resulting
995 from myocardial ischemia and infarction. *Physiological Reviews* 69, 1049–1169. doi:10.1152/physrev.
996 1989.69.4.1049
- 997 Kanda, A., Watanabe, I., Williams, M. L., Engle, C. L., Li, S., Koch, G. G., et al. (1997). Unanticipated
998 lessening of the rise in extracellular potassium during ischemia by pinacidil. *Circulation* 95, 1937–1944.
999 doi:10.1161/01.CIR.95.7.1937
- 1000 Kazbanov, I. V., Clayton, R. H., Nash, M. P., Bradley, C. P., Paterson, D. J., Hayward, M. P., et al.
1001 (2014). Effect of global cardiac ischemia on human ventricular fibrillation: Insights from a multi-scale
1002 mechanistic model of the human heart. *PLOS Computational Biology* 10, 1–15. doi:10.1371/journal.
1003 pcbi.1003891
- 1004 Keller, D., Weber, F. M., Seemann, G., and Dössel, O. (2010). Ranking the influence of tissue conductivities
1005 on forward-calculated ecgs. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 57, 1568–1576. doi:10.
1006 1109/TBME.2010.2046485
- 1007 Kléber, A., Riegger, C. B., and Janse, M. J. (1987). Extracellular K⁺ and H⁺ shifts in early ischemia:
1008 Mechanisms and relation to changes in impulse propagation. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular*
1009 *Cardiology* 19, 35–44. doi:10.1016/S0022-2828(87)80608-9
- 1010 Kléber, A. G. (1983). Resting membrane potential, extracellular potassium activity, and intracellular
1011 sodium activity during acute global ischemia in isolated perfused guinea pig hearts. *Circulation Research*
1012 52, 442–450. doi:10.1161/01.RES.52.4.442
- 1013 Kléber, A. G. (1984). Extracellular potassium accumulation in acute myocardial ischemia. *Journal of*
1014 *Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 16, 389–394. doi:10.1016/S0022-2828(84)80610-0
- 1015 Kléber, A. G., Janse, M. J., van Capelle, F. J., and Durrer, D. (1978). Mechanism and time course of s-t and t-
1016 q segment changes during acute regional myocardial ischemia in the pig heart determined by extracellular
1017 and intracellular recordings. *Circulation Research* 42, 603–613. doi:10.1161/01.RES.42.5.603
- 1018 Kohl, P., Bollensdorff, C., and Garny, A. (2006). Effects of mechanosensitive ion channels on ventricular
1019 electrophysiology: experimental and theoretical models. *Experimental Physiology* 91, 307–321. doi:https:
1020 //doi.org/10.1113/expphysiol.2005.031062
- 1021 Kunze, D. L. (1977). Rate-dependent changes in extracellular potassium in the rabbit atrium. *Circulation*
1022 *Research* 41, 122–127. doi:10.1161/01.RES.41.1.122

- 1023 Li, W., Kohl, P., and Trayanova, N. (2006). Myocardial ischemia lowers precordial thump efficacy: An
1024 inquiry into mechanisms using three-dimensional simulations. *Heart Rhythm* 3, 179–186. doi:10.1016/j.
1025 hrthm.2005.10.033
- 1026 Luo, C. H. and Rudy, Y. (1994). A dynamic model of the cardiac ventricular action potential. i. simulations
1027 of ionic currents and concentration changes. *Circulation Research* 74, 1071–1096. doi:10.1161/01.RES.
1028 74.6.1071
- 1029 Martišienė, I., Jurevičius, J., Vosyliūtė, R., Navalinskas, A., Treinys, R., Mačianskienė, R., et al. (2015).
1030 Evolution of action potential alternans in rabbit heart during acute regional ischemia. *BioMed Research*
1031 *International* 2015, 951704. doi:10.1155/2015/951704
- 1032 Mena Tobar, A., Ferrero, J. M., Migliavacca, F., and Rodriguez Matas, J. F. (2018). Vulnerability
1033 in regionally ischemic human heart. effect of the extracellular potassium concentration. *Journal of*
1034 *Computational Science* 24, 160–168. doi:10.1016/j.jocs.2017.11.009
- 1035 Mitani, A. and Shattock, M. J. (1992). Role of Na-activated K channel, Na – K – Cl cotransport, and
1036 Na – K pump in $[K]_e$ changes during ischemia in rat heart. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and*
1037 *Circulatory Physiology* 263, H333–H340. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1992.263.2.H333
- 1038 Murphy, L., Renodin, D., Antzelevitch, C., Di Diego, J. M., and Cordeiro, J. M. (2011). Extracellular
1039 proton depression of peak and late Na^+ current in the canine left ventricle. *American Journal of*
1040 *Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 301, H936–H944. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.00204.2011.
1041 PMID: 21685271
- 1042 Nakashima, M., Hashimoto, H., Kanamura, M., Nagaya, T., Hashizume, M., and Oishi, H. (1978).
1043 Experimental studies and clinical report on the electrical alternans of ST segment during myocardial
1044 ischemia. *Japanese Heart Journal* 19, 396–408. doi:10.1536/ihj.19.396
- 1045 Niederer, S. (2013). Regulation of ion gradients across myocardial ischemic border zones: A biophysical
1046 modelling analysis. *PLOS ONE* 8, 1–21. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0060323
- 1047 Niederer, S. A., Kerfoot, E., Benson, A. P., Bernabeu, M. O., Bernus, O., Bradley, C., et al. (2011).
1048 Verification of cardiac tissue electrophysiology simulators using an N-version benchmark. *Philosophical*
1049 *Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 369, 4331–4351.
1050 doi:10.1098/rsta.2011.0139
- 1051 O’Hara, T., Virág, L., Varró, A., and Rudy, Y. (2011). Simulation of the undiseased human cardiac
1052 ventricular action potential: Model formulation and experimental validation. *PLOS Computational*
1053 *Biology* 7, 1–29. doi:10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002061
- 1054 Parker, J. O., Chiong, M. A., West, R. O., and Case, R. B. (1970). The effect of ischemia and alterations of
1055 heart rate on myocardial potassium balance in man. *Circulation* 42, 205–217. doi:10.1161/01.CIR.42.2.
1056 205
- 1057 Peyronnet, R., Nerbonne, J. M., and Kohl, P. (2016). Cardiac mechano-gated ion channels and arrhythmias.
1058 *Circulation Research* 118, 311–329. doi:10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.115.305043
- 1059 Potse, M., Coronel, R., LeBlanc, A.-R., and Vinet, A. (2007a). Modeling transport of interstitial potassium
1060 in regional myocardial ischemia: effect on the injury current. In *2007 29th Annual International*
1061 *Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*. 6330–6333. doi:10.1109/IEMBS.
1062 2007.4353803
- 1063 Potse, M., Coronel, R., LeBlanc, A. R., and Vinet, A. (2007b). The role of extracellular potassium
1064 transport in computer models of the ischemic zone. *Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing* 45,
1065 1187–1199. doi:10.1007/s11517-007-0276-9

- 1066 Quinn, T. A. and Kohl, P. (2021). Cardiac mechano-electric coupling: Acute effects of mechanical
1067 stimulation on heart rate and rhythm. *Physiological Reviews* 101, 37–92. doi:10.1152/physrev.00036.
1068 2019
- 1069 Rodríguez, B., Ferrero, J. M., and Trénor, B. (2002). Mechanistic investigation of extracellular K⁺
1070 accumulation during acute myocardial ischemia: a simulation study. *American Journal of Physiology-
1071 Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 283, H490–H500. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.00625.2001
- 1072 Romero, L., Trénor, B., Alonso, J., Tobón, C., Saiz, J., and Ferrero, J. (2009). The relative role of
1073 refractoriness and source–sink relationship in reentry generation during simulated acute ischemia.
1074 *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 37, 1560–1571. doi:10.1007/s10439-009-9721-2
- 1075 Roth, G. A., Mensah, G. A., and Fuster, V. (2020). The global burden of cardiovascular diseases and risks.
1076 *Journal of the American College of Cardiology* 76, 2980–2981. doi:10.1016/j.jacc.2020.11.021
- 1077 Saegusa, N., Moorhouse, E., Vaughan-Jones, R. D., and Spitzer, K. W. (2011). Influence of pH on Ca²⁺
1078 current and its control of electrical and Ca²⁺ signaling in ventricular myocytes. *Journal of General
1079 Physiology* 138, 537–559. doi:10.1085/jgp.201110658
- 1080 Sakamoto, K., Ishikawa, M., Koga, K., Urushidani, T., and Nagao, T. (2000). Energy preserving effect of
1081 l-cis diltiazem in isolated ischemic and reperfused guinea pig hearts: a 31P – NMR study. *The Japanese
1082 Journal of Pharmacology* 83, 225–232. doi:10.1254/jjp.83.225
- 1083 Shivkumar, K., Deutsch, N. A., Lamp, S. T., Khoo, K., Goldhaber, J. I., and Weiss, J. N. (1997).
1084 Mechanism of hypoxic K loss in rabbit ventricle. *The Journal of Clinical Investigation* 100, 1782–1788.
1085 doi:10.1172/JCI119705
- 1086 Smith, W. T., Fleet, W. F., Johnson, T. A., Engle, C. L., and Cascio, W. E. (1995). The Ib phase of
1087 ventricular arrhythmias in ischemic in situ porcine heart is related to changes in cell-to-cell electrical
1088 coupling. *Circulation* 92, 3051–3060. doi:10.1161/01.CIR.92.10.3051
- 1089 Sobel, B. E., Corr, P. B., Robison, A. K., Goldstein, R. A., Witkowski, F. X., and Klein, M. S. (1978).
1090 Accumulation of lysophosphoglycerides with arrhythmogenic properties in ischemic myocardium. *The
1091 Journal of Clinical Investigation* 62, 546–553. doi:10.1172/JCI109159
- 1092 Sutton, P. M. I., Taggart, P., Opthof, T., Coronel, R., Trimlett, R., Pugsley, W., et al. (2000). Repolarisation
1093 and refractoriness during early ischaemia in humans. *Heart* 84, 365–369. doi:10.1136/heart.84.4.365
- 1094 Taggart, P., Sutton, P. M., Opthof, T., Coronel, R., Trimlett, R., Pugsley, W., et al. (2000). Inhomogeneous
1095 transmural conduction during early ischaemia in patients with coronary artery disease. *Journal of
1096 Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 32, 621–630. doi:10.1006/jmcc.2000.1105
- 1097 Terkildsen, J. R., Crampin, E. J., and Smith, N. P. (2007). The balance between inactivation and activation
1098 of the Na⁺ – K⁺ pump underlies the triphasic accumulation of extracellular K⁺ during myocardial
1099 ischemia. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 293, H3036–H3045.
1100 doi:10.1152/ajpheart.00771.2007
- 1101 Tice, B. M., Rodríguez, B., Eason, J., and Trayanova, N. (2007). Mechanistic investigation into the
1102 arrhythmogenic role of transmural heterogeneities in regional ischaemia phase 1A. *EP Europace* 9,
1103 vi46–vi58. doi:10.1093/europace/eum204
- 1104 Tomek, J., Bueno-Orovio, A., Passini, E., Zhou, X., Mincholé, A., Britton, O., et al. (2019). Development,
1105 calibration, and validation of a novel human ventricular myocyte model in health, disease, and drug
1106 block. *eLife* 8, e48890. doi:10.7554/eLife.48890
- 1107 Trénor, B., Romero, L., Ferrero, J., Sáiz, J., Moltó, G., and Alonso, J. (2007). Vulnerability to reentry in
1108 a regionally ischemic tissue: A simulation study. *Annals of Biomedical Engineering* 35, 1756–1770.
1109 doi:10.1007/s10439-007-9353-3

- 1110 Van Wagoner, D. R. (1993). Mechanosensitive gating of atrial atp-sensitive potassium channels. *Circulation*
1111 *Research* 72, 973–983. doi:10.1161/01.RES.72.5.973
- 1112 Vaughan-Jones, R. D., Spitzer, K. W., and Swietach, P. (2009). Intracellular ph regulation in heart. *Journal*
1113 *of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 46, 318–331. doi:10.1016/j.yjmcc.2008.10.024
- 1114 Walfridsson, H., Odman, S., and Lund, N. (1985). Myocardial oxygen pressure across the lateral border
1115 zone after acute coronary occlusion in the pig heart. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 191, 203–210. doi:10.1007/
1116 978-1-4684-3291-6_20
- 1117 Watanabe, I. and Gettes, L. S. (2016). Initial and secondary ST – T alternans during acute myocardial
1118 ischemia in the in-situ pig heart. *International Heart Journal* 57, 327–335. doi:10.1536/ihj.15-337
- 1119 Watanabe, I. and Gettes, L. S. (2018). Effects of verapamil and pinacidil on extracellular K⁺, pH, and
1120 the incidence of ventricular fibrillation during 60 minutes of ischemia. *International Heart Journal* 59,
1121 589–595. doi:10.1536/ihj.17-175
- 1122 Watson, C. L. and Gold, M. R. (1995). Effect of intracellular and extracellular acidosis on sodium
1123 current in ventricular myocytes. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 268,
1124 H1749–H1756. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1995.268.4.H1749
- 1125 Weiss, J. and Shine, K. I. (1981). Extracellular potassium accumulation during myocardial ischemia:
1126 Implications for arrhythmogenesis. *Journal of Molecular and Cellular Cardiology* 13, 699–704.
1127 doi:10.1016/0022-2828(81)90277-7
- 1128 Weiss, J. and Shine, K. I. (1982a). Extracellular K⁺ accumulation during myocardial ischemia in isolated
1129 rabbit heart. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 242, H619–H628.
1130 doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1982.242.4.H619
- 1131 Weiss, J. and Shine, K. I. (1982b). [K⁺]_o accumulation and electrophysiological alterations during
1132 early myocardial ischemia. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 243,
1133 H318–H327. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1982.243.2.H318
- 1134 Weiss, J. and Shine, K. I. (1986). Effects of heart rate on extracellular K⁺ accumulation during myocardial
1135 ischemia. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 250, H982–H991. doi:10.
1136 1152/ajpheart.1986.250.6.H982
- 1137 Weiss, J. N., Lamp, S. T., and Shine, K. I. (1989). Cellular K⁺ loss and anion efflux during myocardial
1138 ischemia and metabolic inhibition. *American Journal of Physiology-Heart and Circulatory Physiology*
1139 256, H1165–H1175. doi:10.1152/ajpheart.1989.256.4.H1165
- 1140 Weiss, J. N., Qu, Z., and Shivkumar, K. (2017). Electrophysiology of hypokalemia and hyperkalemia.
1141 *Circulation: Arrhythmia and Electrophysiology* 10, e004667. doi:10.1161/CIRCEP.116.004667
- 1142 Weiss, J. N., Venkatesh, N., and Lamp, S. T. (1992). ATP-sensitive K⁺ channels and cellular K⁺ loss in
1143 hypoxic and ischaemic mammalian ventricle. *The Journal of Physiology* 447, 649–673. doi:10.1113/
1144 jphysiol.1992.sp019022
- 1145 Wilde, A. A. and Aksnes, G. (1995). Myocardial potassium loss and cell depolarisation in ischaemia and
1146 hypoxia. *Cardiovascular Research* 29, 1–15. doi:10.1016/S0008-6363(96)88539-7
- 1147 Wilde, A. A., Escande, D., Schumacher, C. A., Thuringer, D., Mestre, M., Fiolet, J. W., et al. (1990).
1148 Potassium accumulation in the globally ischemic mammalian heart. a role for the ATP-sensitive
1149 potassium channel. *Circulation Research* 67, 835–843. doi:10.1161/01.RES.67.4.835
- 1150 Yan, G. X., Chen, J., Yamada, K. A., Kléber, A. G., and Corr, P. B. (1996). Contribution of shrinkage of
1151 extracellular space to extracellular K⁺ accumulation in myocardial ischaemia of the rabbit. *The Journal*
1152 *of Physiology* 490, 215–228. doi:10.1113/jphysiol.1996.sp021137

- 1153 Yan, G.-X., Joshi, A., Guo, D., Hlaing, T., Martin, J., Xu, X., et al. (2004). Phase 2 reentry as a trigger
1154 to initiate ventricular fibrillation during early acute myocardial ischemia. *Circulation* 110, 1036–1041.
1155 doi:10.1161/01.CIR.0000140258.09964.19

7 TABLES

Table 1. Model parameters for the electrophysiology and transport equations.

Parameter	Definition	Value	Unit
C_m	Membrane specific capacitance	1.0	$\mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^2$
L	Cable length	4.0	cm
D_V	Effective tissue conductivity	0.0026	mS
F	Faraday constant	96486	C/mol
A_c	Cell capacitive surface	0.0152	mm^2
v_o	Extracellular cleft volume	13.3	μm^3
S_v^i	Intracellular surface to volume ratio	363.6	mm^{-1}
S_v^e	Extracellular surface to volume ratio	127.3	mm^{-1}
D_K	$[K^+]_e$ diffusion coefficient	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	cm^2/ms
$[K^+]_b$	$[K^+]_e$ bulk concentration	5.4	mM
τ_{wo}	Normoxic wash-out time constant	15	s

FIGURES AND CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Time course of ischemia-related parameters in the simulated cell (“0D simulations”, panels A-D) and spatial profiles in the simulated tissue (“1D simulations”, panel E). A: Intracellular ATP concentration. We adopted the time course reported by Sakamoto et al. (2000) for guinea-pig (at 37°C) with the normoxic value of O’Hara et al. (2011) and Cao et al. (2018). **B:** Intracellular ADP concentration, assuming a time course as reported by Terkildsen et al. (2007), based on Befroy et al. (1999) for guinea-pig at 37°C. **C:** Intracellular and extracellular pH, adopting the time course for guinea-pig reported by Sakamoto et al. (2000) (at 37°C) and a normoxic value for pH_o by Vaughan-Jones et al. (2009). **D:** Intracellular LPC concentration, assumed linear and estimated using data from Gautier et al. (2008) in rat at 22°C and Daleau (1999) for guinea-pig at 30°C. **E:** Spatial profiles of the ischemic parameters in relation to the simulated 1D tissue. As an example, values within the ischemic part of the strand correspond to 10 minutes post-occlusion (dashed lines in panels A-D). A pH transition zone (pH TZ) was assumed to be 0.5 cm wide (Coronel et al. (1988)). pH was assumed to vary linearly within that zone.

Figure 2. Extracellular potassium accumulation and transmembrane potassium fluxes. A: Extracellular potassium concentration ($[K^+]_o$) vs time in an isolated ventricular cardiomyocyte subject to progressive ischemia. Solid blue line: simulated result; black circles: experimental data adapted from Wilde and Aksnes (Wilde and Aksnes, 1995). B: Simulated time course of $[K^+]_o$ for different heart rates (bpm: beats per minute). C: Unidirectional potassium efflux rate (green), influx rate (black) and net efflux rate (black) vs time.

Figure 3. Potassium transmembrane fluxes carried by individual ionic currents. A: Simulated ischemic $[K^+]_o$ vs time in an isolated ventricular cardiomyocyte. B-F: Individual contributions of potassium currents to potassium transmembrane flux rates. Cyan coloured bars indicate efflux rates (when positive) or influx rates (when negative). Blue bars show total efflux and influx rates. Red bar indicates net efflux rate.

Figure 4. Simulated APs and selected ionic currents in an acutely ischemic isolated ventricular cardiomyocyte. Top row (black traces): consecutive APs 0.0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0 and 20.0 minutes after the onset of progressive ischemia. Lower rows (blue traces): inward rectifier potassium current (I_{K1}), ATP-sensitive potassium current ($I_{K(ATP)}$), rapid delayed rectifier potassium current (I_{Kr}), and sodium/potassium pump (I_{NaK}), respectively.

Figure 5. Relationship between simulated extracellular potassium concentration and APs. A: time course of $[K^+]_o$ (upper graph) and APD at 90% repolarization (lower graph), showing the AP alternating phase (dashed vertical lines). B: simulated AP alternans corresponding to the 4.6 minute mark. The time axis has been broken to enhance the shape of the “short” and “long” APs. C-F: Action potentials (upper black traces) and $[K^+]_o$ (lower blue traces) showing the “micro” fluctuations in extracellular potassium concentration. The * symbols indicate diastolic minimum potassium levels.

Figure 6. Spatial profile of extracellular potassium accumulation. A: spatial profile in the tissue preparation at different times from the onset of ischemia. B: influence of the tissue conductivity and extracellular potassium diffusion coefficient on the extracellular potassium spatial profile at 30 minutes from the onset of ischemia.

Figure 7. Extracellular potassium flux rates. A,B: Extracellular potassium accumulation (Panel A) and extracellular potassium diffusion flux rate (Panel B) for a point located in the BZ. C,D: Extracellular potassium accumulation (Panel C) and extracellular potassium diffusion flux rate (Panel D) for a point located in the CIZ.

Figure 8. Electrophysiological manifestations of the extracellular potassium accumulation in tissue. A: time course of the $[K^+]_o$ at different locations in the tissue. Model results at the BZ are compared with experimental results (Coronel et al., 1988). B: Evolution of the APD₉₀ during acute ischemia in different locations. C: Evolution of the AP during ischemia at different positions in the tissue. D: Changes in the electrograms with ischemia at different locations in the tissue. Arrows indicate the depression in the ST segment due to ischemia in the altered region.

Figure 9. Injury current during acute regional ischemia. A: Action potentials at three different locations within the cable at two instances after the onset of ischemia. B: Simulated electrograms at the same positions and time instants as in panel B. C: Intracellular depolarizing current at the moment the depolarizing front enters the ischemic region. D: Intracellular injury current at the moment of deepest negative T-wave in the ischemic zone and during the diastolic phase.